

Technical Brochure

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for the Black Sea (DOORS)
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Technical Brochure

This brochure presents a comprehensive overview of the DOORS (Developing Optimal and Open Research Support) project, funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101000518.

It serves as an accessible resource for stakeholders, researchers, and the wider public, offering insights into the project’s goals, methodologies, and key outcomes and highlighting DOORS’ efforts to build a shared understanding and sustainable future for the Black Sea.

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Executive Summary

The H2020 DOORS (Developing Optimal and Open Research Support for the Black Sea) project responds to the urgent need to better understand and protect the Black Sea — a region rich in biodiversity, history, and economic potential, yet heavily impacted by human activities, climate change, and geopolitical tensions. Led by GeoEcoMar Romania and comprising 35 institutions, DOORS operationalizes the Black Sea Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), aiming to deliver a healthy, productive, and resilient marine environment.

DOORS is structured around three interconnected programmes:

- **System of Systems (SoS):** Integrates diverse data sources into a unified portal to enhance scientific understanding and support stakeholder decision-making, laying foundations for a future Digital Twin of the Black Sea.
- **Blue Growth Accelerator (BGA):** Identifies and supports sustainable innovation and entrepreneurship in Blue Economy sectors, while fostering public-private partnerships.
- **Knowledge Transfer and Training (KTT):** Strengthens collaboration between science, policy, and society through training, capacity building, and promoting ocean literacy and citizen science.

By combining cutting-edge research, technology, education, and stakeholder engagement, DOORS is paving the way for a sustainable and prosperous future for the Black Sea region, aligned with the goals of the European Green Deal and the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters."

Introduction

Bordering six countries (Romania, Bulgaria, Ukraine, Russia, Georgia and Türkiye), and bridging two continents (Europe and Asia) the Black Sea is unique in its geological history, specific ecosystems and cultural heritage. Around 16 million people live along the Black Sea coastline, bound by a shared heritage that stretches back to Ancient Greek settlements and, more recently, by the enduring legacies of communist rule and ongoing geopolitical tensions.

The Black Sea is the world's largest inland sea and is also the largest meromictic basin, with lower and upper water layers that do not intermix. This limited vertical circulation results in oxygen being confined to the surface layers, which alone can support complex marine life, being home to specific ecosystems, some of which are rarely found in other seas. In contrast, the deeper layers remain anoxic – devoid of oxygen – sustaining only microbial life forms, primarily specialized bacteria adapted to these extreme conditions.

The cumulative impact of invasive species, overfishing, pollution – both from the coasts as well as from the rivers bringing here their waters – and other human influences caused a major environmental crisis three decades ago, from which the Sea continues to recover. This fragile rehabilitation is threatened by new challenges including new chemical pollutants, litter and microplastics. Combined with extensive eutrophication (high levels of phosphorous, nitrogen and other nutrients), fish stocks and species diversity remain under significant pressure, putting communities and livelihoods at risk. The impacts of Climate Change accumulate with the effects from human activities and the war in Ukraine, and these pressures put the Black Sea environment at a major amount of stress. The recent destruction of Ukraine's Kakhovka Dam presented a shock to the already fragile ecosystem.

This is the reason why we need to know as much as possible about the Black Sea. About its ecosystems, about the processes occurring here – from the coasts and river mouths to the deepest parts of the sea. And this is where the H2020 DOORS Black Sea project comes into play.

Our Mission

DOORS main objectives are to make operational the Black Sea SRIA, to support the successful Blue Growth implementation and to contribute to a healthy, productive and resilient Black Sea.

The DOORS Project

Developing Optimal and Open Research Support for the Black Sea (DOORS) is a €9m EU Research and Innovation project, following on from the SRIA, which brings together expertise and technology from 35 institutions from the Black Sea region and other European countries. Linking science, citizens and industry together to address the human and climate change impacts in the marine ecosystem, it has driven critical regeneration across the Black Sea region through identifying and enabling Blue Growth opportunities.

DOORS is led by the National Institute for Research and Development of Marine Geology and Geoecology - GeoEcoMar, Romania, under the general coordination of Professor Adrian Stănică.

Between 2021 and 2025, the DOORS project has undertaken major research and innovation activities across three key programs: the System of Systems (SoS) to enhance observation, modelling and analytical capabilities; the Blue Growth Accelerators (BGA) which aims to develop the region's blue economy; and

Knowledge Transfer and Training (KTT) bringing together researchers, policymakers and communities to supporting evidence-based decision making, and build capacity through meaningful stakeholder engagement.

The DOORS Programmes

Building on decades of research, DOORS translates the four pillars of the Black Sea Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) into actionable outcomes, advancing the goals of both the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters" and the broader European Green Deal.

State of the art technology allows a science-based appreciation of the entire Black Sea like never before, increasing awareness of the Sea's fragility, and enabling novel solutions and policy approaches to be considered. Every part of the region can benefit, empowering decision makers and investors to unlock the area's enormous potential for 'Blue Growth' (economic prosperity centred on the sustainable use of marine resources).

Managed appropriately, the Black Sea can provide a sustainable foundation for industries from fishing, aquaculture and maritime transport through to renewables, technology and education. The region's untapped tourist potential is also significant. The Black Sea's unique geological history has created a phenomenon where oxygen is absent below depths of 180-200 metres, with most marine species living only in the upper, oxygenated layer. This lack of oxygen in deeper layers means that the historical legacy of previous centuries is uniquely preserved. The world's oldest known intact shipwreck, a 2,400-year-old Greek merchant ship, was discovered in 2018. Significant scope exists for research, archaeological exploration and heritage tourism to transform this common history into a shared future.

The opportunities for the region's many millions of inhabitants are unparalleled but can only be realised fully with the right combination of expertise, experience and innovation. Science, industry, policymakers and citizens need to work together to explore and identify prospects for growth that can maximise prosperity for the region and its communities.

The European Union has already set an ambitious framework for this collaboration. The Common Maritime Agenda for the Black Sea, launched in 2019, details a shared vision and commitment among regional partners, centres of marine expertise and the European Commission, to pursue a "productive, healthy, resilient, sustainable and better-valued Black Sea by 2030". Greater maritime cooperation will help to better connect Black Sea societies "through a bridge of new knowledge, technologies and services", which promise to unlock unique opportunities for "sustainable and environmentally friendly blue growth".

At the heart of this effort is the Black Sea Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), which recognises the transformative power of science and technology. The SRIA guides researchers, industry and policy makers to better understand the shared ecosystem, processes and challenges facing the Black Sea, to promote the social well-being and prosperity of its citizens, and to support economic growth and jobs in those countries bordering it.

These ambitions are delivered through three integrated key work programmes:

1. System of Systems (SoS)

A platform designed to bring together, for the first time, multiple data streams from different sources and formats and harmonises these through a Data Cube, which provides a common data model and format: from information coming from satellites to samples measured in situ, data coming from cruises to results from numerical simulations. This facilitates a single smart intuitive portal that allows to understand, in near-real

time, what is going on in the Black Sea. The information provided can help the various categories of stakeholders – from the simple public and local authorities to persons involved in Blue Economy activities and beyond.

Three DOORS cruises performed in 2023-2024. These cruises have managed to bring in a lot of completely novel information about the state of the Black Sea. Details of the cruises are reported in the relevant chapters for the experimental work done in the DOORS.

The SoS also brings together other sources of data already operational –the SOS Dashboard – that also give access to many other sources, which in turn, bring in different information that can be of use for many different categories of stakeholders in contact with the sea.

This is just a first step in what should become a real Digital Twin of the Black Sea. But for this we need a much more intense and longer-term effort.

2. Blue Growth Accelerator (BGA)

Our BGA enabled identification of sectors and entrepreneurs for innovation, provided professional support to unlock their potential, enhanced the exploitation of knowledge, and facilitated networking and constructive exchange between scientists, entrepreneurs and policy makers for sustainable development of Blue Growth sectors.

Part of the BGA is the Black Sea Accelerator (BSA). BSA was generated together with the H2020 BRIDGE-BS project and opened the gates to practical knowledge and education in the spirit of blue business development with practical support in aspects that were requested by the participants.

Bringing together public and private investments was a must. DOORS brought in front some of the most respected individuals interested in the transformation of the Black Sea in a sustainable environment and thus creating a Special Interest Group for the Black Sea.

3. Knowledge Transfer and Training (KTT)

KTT built upon existing collaborations and established new ones between actors in science and policy, fostering a culture of openness and facilitating the exchange of best practices and knowledge.

Training exercises – for young researchers, students and other categories of interested persons have been run through the DOORS KTT programs, such as: the Early-Stage Researcher Exchange (ESRE) program; the Mutual Mobilisation Learning (MMLs) workshops series across the Black Sea (in two rounds - in Romania, Bulgaria, Georgia, Moldova, Türkiye, Ukraine); Lifelong online training courses and learning materials (designed for vocational learners) and; Train the trainers.

The DOORS project has actively fostered Ocean Literacy and Citizen Science to bridge the gap between scientific research, policy, and public engagement, as well as to enhance public involvement in marine stewardship.

1. Focus on System of Systems (SoS): A one-stop-shop for standardised data and model outputs to drive evidence-based knowledge development for the Black Sea

The DOORS System of Systems (SoS) is a first of its kind digital platform that integrates heterogeneous data from multiple sources to provide a comprehensive environmental systems understanding of the Black Sea. Data from in-situ measurements, sensor arrays, satellite-based Earth observation, external repositories, and numerical model outputs are combined in a single interactive platform to support informed decision making.

Image: The System of System architecture © DOORS

The SoS provides a robust and user-friendly Data Cube Framework with Analysis Ready Data for accessing, exploring, and managing marine and environmental data related to the Black Sea. It is built on two core components of a Data Cube framework: the xcube Viewer and the xcube Server, which together deliver an interactive and scalable data exploration experience.

The **xcube Viewer** serves as the primary user interface for the SoS platform, enabling interactive exploration of gridded data sets collected and processed through the DOORS project. It supports the implementation of various Use Cases, allowing stakeholders to gain valuable insights into the state of the Black Sea.

The viewer is continuously available as a live service at: <https://doors.viewer.brockmann-consult.de>

Key features include:

- A responsive and intuitive interface for visualizing complex environmental data
- Integration of thematic layers and time series data
- User and access management to support personalized experiences and secure data sharing

Supporting the viewer is the **xcube Server**, which functions as the backend providing access to all gridded

data sets. The server can be reached through a well-defined API: <https://doors.api.brockmann-consult.de/api/openapi.html>

This API offers endpoints to clients which may request meta information about the data sets or sections of data variables ingested into the **xcube goodb**. For a selection of these datasets, dedicated visualisation forms were put in place in the form of dashboards. Also, using the aforementioned API, these datasets may be fed into the viewer (the DOORS JupyterLab offers full access to these datasets).

The software is fully open source and permits a rapid access to time series data, swiftly created for regions and variables of interest. Providing access to real and near-real time data, the SoS allows the monitoring current and unforeseen events such as the explosion at the Kakhovka Dam in Ukraine on 6th June 2023, the Bettina Storm in November 2023, the biggest one ever recorded, or moments when the algae bloom in the Black Sea.

Image: Assessing the impact (Chlorophyll-a concentration, CMEMS) of the explosion at the Kakhovka Dam in Ukraine on 6th June 2023 © DOORS

Image: Black Sea extreme events: Wave height data during Storm Bettina hitting the Western Black Sea the night from 18th to 19th November 2023 © DOORS

The ingested data are well documented, specific to the different users’ needs, including data forecasts or the DOORS in-situ data sets, and the software provides [interactive user guide](#) and user manual on how expert users can further develop it.

The SOS design involved engaging with diverse groups of stakeholders as well as DOORS partners from the very beginning. This ensures a highly valued and adaptable, basin-scale Observation System fully adhering to FAIR principles for data, tools, products and services. This early involvement enabled stakeholders not only to co-develop the design and to help shape a system tailored to their needs, but also to ensure they could actively use it and retrieve relevant data from it.

Country	Blue Economy Priorities								Environmental Challenges								
	Aquaculture	Capture Fisheries	Data for Evidence	Marine R&D	Oil & Gas	Renewable Energy	Shipping & Ports	Tourism incl. Coastal & Marine	Biodiversity	Climate change Extreme Events	Coastal Erosion	Environmental Shocks	Eutrophication	Marine litter	Over fishing	Pollution, incl. sources	Water level
Ukraine				●								●	●	●		●	
Romania	●	●		●		●		●		●	●		●	●		●	
Moldova								●	●								●
Bulgaria		●		●			●	●	●	●	●		●	●		●	
Türkiye	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	
Georgia	●	●	●	●			●	●		●	●		●	●	●	●	
Basin Wide			●	●				●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	

Image: Sos Co-Development: Stakeholder Priority Areas © DOORS

The SoS is designed to:

- Bring together complex data streams into analysis (or even interpretation), based on ready data cubes using the same (meta)data standard and format;
- Deliver harmonised spatial and temporal data products (sampling, cruises, fixed and mobile oceanographic platforms, Earth observations and numerical models);
- Support the needs of stakeholders, using FAIR principles;
- Support knowledge transfer and build a common understanding;
- Support sustainable innovation in the Blue Economy for the region (Blue Growth Accelerator).

The SoS integrates with DOORS work that aims to improve data accuracy through standardisation and new models as we have:

- Created a harmonised set of methodologies for sampling, measurement, analysis and modelling, based on existing best practices. This enables all the Black Sea coastal countries to use FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) compliant data (existing and new).

- Built, for the first time, full chains connecting models from the Black Sea catchments to the open sea (including liquid, solid and nutrient loads for 11 main rivers flowing into the Black Sea). This allows the characterising and quantifying effects of storm surges, waves, eutrophication, marine litter dispersal, sediment paths and river areas of influence.
- Applied the latest techniques supported by state of the art and next generation in situ sensors. This helps to characterise surface, sub-surface and benthic state of the Black Sea.
- Developed new algorithms to improve the satellite Earth observation data product accuracy. This helps the retrieval of water quality parameters, such as the eutrophic status, sediment flux and coastal erosion, along with novel techniques to map microplastic distribution from space.
- Used models to support relevant plans for adaptation to climate change scenarios.

Harmonised Methods for Data Collection, Storage and Handling

As climate change accelerates, the demand for accurate, high-quality marine data is more critical than ever. The Black Sea, a region particularly vulnerable to environmental shifts, requires harmonised data collection, curation, and dissemination following international standards.

By standardising how data is gathered, formatted, and stored, data harmonisation enables seamless integration and comparison of datasets across institutions, countries, and disciplines and supports robust scientific analysis, informed decision-making, and effective environmental monitoring. Harmonisation also facilitates long-term data accessibility and reuse, ensuring that valuable information remains usable for future research, policy formulation, and regional cooperation initiatives.

Starting with mapping of knowledge gaps and needs and creating a harmonised set of methodologies for sampling, measurement, analysis and modelling, based on existing best practices, DOORS has made significant progress for a common language in Black Sea science. A DOORS Black Sea Data Harmonisation Manual was produced for the first time in the region in order to promote a more efficient scientific cooperation at the basin scale by establishing compatible protocols and methods. The Manual provides extensive analysis, guidelines and recommendations on standardised research methods and data collection (through monitoring, sampling, laboratory analysis, storage and handling), together with recommendations for the collection of data according to FAIR principles. It is also a valuable tool for implementation of policies related to the marine issues (e.g. implementation of Directives – MSFD, WFD, MSP etc.)

Advancing Marine Science in the Black Sea: In Situ Observations

Several scientific activities from the DOORS consortium, mentioned below, were established to advance knowledge on the marine environment in the Black Sea.

Three DOORS cruises conducted in 2023 and 2024 successfully delivered a wealth of novel insights into the current state of the Black Sea despite the ongoing war in Ukraine, which has posed significant risks to the Black Sea and restricted research activities. These missions were meticulously planned, with strict safety protocols implemented on board to ensure the well-being of all participants. Thanks to this careful coordination, the DOORS Black Sea cruises research programme was fully carried out, significantly enhancing our scientific understanding of the region and contributing valuable data to the SoS.

Image: R/V Mare Nigrum and some of the instruments utilized during DOORS cruises © DOORS

DOORS researchers studied specific and unique processes from the shores of the Black Sea to the deeper parts, the gas hydrate deposits from the abyssal part of the Black Sea. For the first time in the history of Black Sea research a robotic glider was deployed – and operated for about one month and a half. We managed to test novel sensors and tools.

Image: Summary of the three DOORS Cruise Campaigns 2023-2024 © DOORS

DOORS Cruise 1 (1-20 May, 2023) employed a wide array of oceanographic and environmental measurements. Activities included microplastic sampling using Neuston and Manta nets and a Van Veen grab, current profiling via ADCP, and the deployment of two EuroARGO floats ('Dolphin' and 'Siren'). The floats have been funded by IO-BAS and EuroArgo ERIC. EuroArgo ERIC continuously monitors them to ensure the proper functioning of the platforms and sensors.

Image: Profiling Argo float deployment © DOORS

Argo floats are autonomous robots. They can't swim, but they can drift with currents, dive in the water column and get back to the surface. Each float dives vertically by inflating or deflating an external bladder to change its buoyancy, much in the same way fish do. Their mission is to collect observations in the open sea. These observations are useful to better understand and predict what happens in the sea and also to monitor the impact of climate change.

Images: Nets for Floating Microplastics Sampling (Left) and Example of microplastics fragments shapes and sizes (Right). The blue bar represents a scale of 1000 μm © DOORS

GeoEcoMar and HCMR jointly investigated floating microplastics (FMPs) abundances and distribution across the western Black Sea surface water using a comprehensive start-to-finish comparison technique involving two sampling methodologies and two spectrometric evaluations for the first time in the area. Moreover, MGEC studied the impact of sediment contamination by microplastics on the ecological condition of the basin. Polypropylene and polyethylene are the dominating materials. The bottom sediments of the continental slope contain a greater quantity of microplastics compared to those of the shelf zone. This difference may be due to hydrodynamic, hydrochemical, and hydrobiological characteristics of the area of study together with the geological process of sedimentation.

This cruise marked a milestone with the **first-ever glider deployment in the Black Sea**: the SOCIB partner deployed a Teledyne Webb Slocum G3 glider perpendicular to the Romanian Shelf for a total of 43 days (May 5th – June 17th, 2023).

Image: SOCIB Teledyne Webb Slocum G3 glider deployment © DOORS

The glider payload included a Seabird Glider payload CTD, an Aanderaa Optode, WETLabs Eco triplet, and Biosperical Instrument sensor, enabling measurements of pressure, temperature, conductivity, oxygen, chlorophyll, CDOM fluorescence, optical backscatter at 700 nm, and photosynthetically active radiation. Throughout the mission, the glider travelled over a distance of 447 nautical miles, performing 10 sections from the shelf to the open Sea, completing 1349 profiles.

Images: Bathymetric map of the study region with the depth - average velocity of each glider section © DOORS

Additional DOORS Cruise 1 efforts included measuring apparent optical properties, sediment sampling for geochemical analysis using a multicorer, microbiological sampling, and the recovery of two Ifremer-launched piezometers, which had collected 19 months of continuous data.

Based on piezometers recordings, Ifremer researchers sought to understand how faults are activated by monitoring the variations in temperature and pressure within the first few meters of submarine sediments across two faults separated by 790 meters. [Their study](#), has been published in the *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*; it shows that the terrestrial tides may influence the behaviour of submarine faults and impact the pressure of fluids trapped within sedimentary layers along these faults.

Images: (Left) DOORS research team and (Right) Instruments used in the DOORS Black Sea cruise: (a) filtration system in the lab, (b) Hyper-OCR radiometer, (c) TriOS radiometer, and (d) optical cage © DOORS

One of the objectives of the DOORS cruises 1 and 2 - Leg 1 was production of state-of-the-art bio-optical measurements including apparent and inherent optical properties of seawater, in addition to the concentration of optically significant constituents. The oceanographic campaigns led to the completion of 65 bio-optical measurement stations of which 42 were collected during DOORS cruise 1 and 23 during DOORS cruise 2 - Leg 1.

Images: Location of the bio-optical measurement stations performed during R/V Mare Nigrum DOORS cruises: (Left) DOORS cruise 1 (May 01-20, 2023) and (Right) DOORS cruise 2, Leg 1 (September 01-10, 2023) © DOORS

The new data collected during DOORS oceanographic campaigns in 2023 as well as existing bio-optical datasets from past cruises and autonomous radiometers (AERONET–OC sites Galata, Gloria and Section -7) operated in the Black Sea were ingested into the DOORS SoS. These data sets were used for assessment of CMEMS OLCI, CMEMS MULTI sensor, CERTO OLCI and CERTO MSI Ocean colour products for the Black Sea.

Table: Bio-optical quantities determined during the DOORS cruises 1 and 2 - Leg 1 © DOORS

Quantity	Symbol	Instrument/Method
Remote sensing reflectance	R_{rs}	Trios, So-rad, Satlantic MicroPro
Total absorption coefficient	a	WetLabs AC-S
Attenuation coefficient	c	WetLabs AC-S
Absorption coefficient of pigmented particles	a_{ph}	Spectrometry
Absorption coefficient of non-pigmented particles	a_{nap}	Spectrometry
Absorption coefficient of coloured diss. organic matter	a_y	Spectrometry
Scattering coefficient	b	WetLabs ECO-BB3
Backscattering coefficient	b_b	WetLabs ECOBB3B
Salinity and temperature	S&T&	CTDs
Total suspended matter	TSM	filtration and weighting
Chlorophyll a concentration	CHL	HPLC, Spectrophotometry
Phytoplankton species analysis with specific reference to coccolithophorite determination	PHY	Inverted microscope
Aerosol optical thickness	τ_a	MICROTOPS Sunphotometer
Secchi depth	SD	Secchi Disk

DOORS Cruise 2 – Leg 1 (1-10 September, 2023) was dedicated to the study of critical and unique seafloor habitats. The primary focus was assessing ecosystem conditions, biodiversity status, and the capacity of these systems to deliver key ecosystem services.

Given the current geopolitical context, we have modified the initial plan which foresaw also the assessment of the ecological quality status of the unique red alga *Phyllophora spp.* field on the NW Black Sea shelf, an important generator of oxygen, involved in nutrients cycle and carbon pump regulation. Since that was not possible because of the war in the region, we decided to investigate a habitat with similar biotope conditions, located slightly southern to the initial proposed area, in the Romanian territorial waters. The main goal was to assess the nutrients cycling capacity of sediments and the influence of faunal activity on benthic turnover rates (CO₂ release, O₂ consumption, nutrient release from sediments) through ex-situ sediment core incubation. The data acquisition focused on three main benthic habitats, as follows: coarse and mixed biogenic type of substrata suitable for thriving of mussel's biogenic reefs and soft-bottom sediments under river plume influence. The obtained data was analysed in relation with water column parameters. In addition, sun-photometric radiance and optical properties of water analyses were performed, which targeted the shallow transitional waters.

In addition, a FerryBox system was used to measure surface seawater temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, chlorophyll fluorescence, chromophoric dissolved organic matter and pH.

DOORS Cruise 2 – Leg 2 (11-20 September, 2023) was dedicated to gas hydrates and gas seepages. Objectives included recovering natural gas hydrates, mapping the upper part of the hydrate stability zone of the gas hydrates by identifying the methane-sulphate transition zone within the sediments, and measuring sediment heat flow – particularly in hydrate-rich zones. Researchers also examined the impacts of methane release from anoxic sediments on the water column, from both geochemical and microbial biodiversity perspectives.

Image: Black Sea gas hydrate deposits (IO-BAS, updated 2023) © DOORS

Evaluating the occurrence of geo-hazards and their potential impact on the marine ecosystems – along with modelling and gas hydrates distribution assessment using special approaches and techniques (e.g. weighted overlay etc.) – has laid the groundwork for developing of a methodology to assess gas hydrates distribution zones in the Black Sea.

This methodology included:

- A consistent analysis of geological processes within the zones of occurrence of gas hydrates in the Black Sea and tested areas;

- The creation of a comprehensive database of gas hydrates in the Black Sea;
- Identification of the main elements and indicators of gas hydrates abundance in the different geomorphological zones (source, pathway, trap) and their proxies, for mapping;
- Determination of input parameters for modelling and compilation of layers (data) for GIS-modelling;
- Spatial analysis and modelling of gas hydrates distribution and forecast including special approaches and techniques (e.g. weighted overlay etc.).

This model could be applied to improving the Black Sea model of the gas hydrates stability zone (GHSZ), assess the abundance of sediment-hosted gas hydrates, and assess potential geohazards and risks.

During this cruise novel sensors developed under the H2020 DOORS project were tested, and intercomparison studies were conducted to support methods harmonisation. NOC lab-on-chip (LOC) prototype in-situ hydrogen sulphide sensor was successfully deployed and measured a vertical hydrogen sulphide profile down to 1500 m depth with promising results.

Image: NOC lab-on-chip (LOC) prototype in-situ hydrogen sulphide sensor (in the left-side of the image; in the right-side there is the battery module) © DOORS

Hereon deployed three instruments for in-situ measurements: 1) an in-situ UV-spectrometer for measurement of hydrogen sulphides for intercomparison with NOC new LOC sensor, 2) a Pocket-FerryBox to survey essential ocean variables and 3) a commercially available CO₂ sensor, HydroC[®]-CO₂-FT pCO₂ sensor (4H-Jena) in order to calculate surface DIC and total alkalinity concentrations, which were compared to discrete water samples for TA and DIC, which will be used to supervise the water column acidification.

DOORS Cruise 3 (1-20 June, 2024) featured an extensive suite of measurements and sampling efforts. These included CTD and ADCP profiling, microplastic analysis in surface waters, water columns, and bottom sediments, as well as sediment characterization (grain size, TOC, chlorophyll-a, carbohydrates, macrofauna).

The cruise also covered benthic flux measurements (O₂, nutrients, CH₄, N₂O), nutrient profiling in the water column, and methane production and consumption zonation studies.

Image: Metagenomic assessment of methane producers in the anoxic waters and sediments of the Black Sea © DOORS

EMOBON protocol sampling was applied for microbiological analyses, and an intercomparison was conducted between a commercial methane sensor (METS by Franatec) and CTD/Niskin water samples.

Further activities included deploying BGC Argo floats in Georgian waters, sampling optically active constituents (chlorophyll-a, TSM, CDOM), assessing apparent and inherent optical properties, conducting sun-photometric measurements, and carrying out geoarchaeological investigations in Georgian coastal zones.

Image: Geoarchaeological investigation of historical Asparos, offshore Gonio city, Georgia © DOORS

During DOORS Cruise 3, underwater archaeological sites were investigated using cutting edge geophysical equipment in the Georgian coastal zone, as well as professional divers. The investigated area is situated near Gonio, a site close to the dynamic Chorokhi River mouth, that was chosen based on historical references. The survey identified for the first time a cluster of geometric features located 200–300 meters from the current coastline. Structures with wall-like shapes, 3–8 meters long, rising about 0.5 meters above the seafloor, arranged in nearly right-angled patterns were detected. A second exciting discovery was a probable shipwreck, around 20 meters long and 2.3 meters wide, lying upright and partially embedded in sediments.

Monitoring Cold-Seep Emissions at the Shallow Bulgarian Coastal Shelf (METZE)

DOORS partners (Ifremer, HCMR, Io-BAS and GeoMarine) created a 3-survey program to investigate the spatial and temporal variabilities of methane emissions at the seafloor, its fate in the water column, and the fluxes at the sediment/sea bottom interface at Varna Lake and the Zelenka coast.

At Varna Lake, the activities focused on assessing the origin of the methane measured by the commercial METS sensor deployed at Geomarine’s automated buoy system and a more accurate quantification of the methane dissolved in the water column. The research involved visual inspections of the lake’s seafloor under automated buoy system by Ifremer divers and the collection of sediment and water samples, aiming to provide a more accurate assessment of the methane dissolved in the water column. These insights are essential to understanding methane’s behaviour in this enclosed water body.

The METS methane sensor was deployed for 70 and 100 days in Fall 2022 and Spring 2023, respectively. Data shows two competing phenomena:

- Seasonal increase of methane concentrations: microbial of methane production sediments.
- Daily methane maximum during night hours: due to convective mixing in the upper layers of water column.

Image: Dissolved CH₄ and temperature temporal overall (Left) and maxima (Right) evolution at Varna Lake (Bulgaria) study-case © DOORS

On Zelenka Beach, the researchers built on the work started two years prior, studying the spatial and temporal variability of methane emissions, which consist of 99% methane with trace amounts of ethane, propane, and carbon dioxide. This study expanded the sampling gas bubbles and water to 12 emission sites to verify the consistency of gas composition and flux over time. Extended [underwater footage](#) carried out by free divers and the 3D reconstruction of the area were conducted to better understand the emission sources.

When comparing these findings with data from 2022 and 2023, the Zelenka Seepages did not show spatial variability of the gas composition:

Image: Comparison of flowrate emissions between morning and afternoon surrounding a carbonate rock, Zelenka Beach © DOORS

Isotopic analysis ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$, δD) of gas bubbles indicates a microbial origin of methane. There is also evidence that methane oxidation rates change seasonally.

Earth Observation (EO): Improving Satellite Products

In DOORS we have implemented and adopted the Optical Water Type (OWT) methodology from the H2020 CERTO project and compared outputs with CMEMS using a robust procedure to match the satellite data products against the most comprehensive in situ validation data set collated for the Black Sea. This in itself demonstrates the value of partnership and collaboration that the DOORS project has forged in the Black Sea region. A series of recommendations have been developed from this exercise that will feed into the next generation of CMEMS products for the Black Sea, enabling: improved atmospheric correction; better spatial coverage of satellite data; and improvements to product accuracy, especially at higher levels of chlorophyll a concentration in the north-western parts of the Black Sea.

Optical water type (OWT) analysis based on fuzzy logic c-means clustering is an unsupervised machine learning technique, used in projects such as the Ocean Colour- (OC) and Lakes-Climate Change Initiatives (CCI). The methodology allows more flexible representation of water province transition zones than classic hard clustering techniques, such as the popular k-means algorithm. Fuzzy OWT classes built around spectral data from coastal transitional waters (including river mouth deltas, lagoons, and estuaries) within the European Horizon 2020 CERTO project have been used to classify the optical variability of the Black Sea, with particular focus on the key study regions in Bulgaria, Romania, Ukraine, Georgia and Turkey. Thus, far in the project, an OWT timeseries of the Black Sea from OLCI data based on the CERTO global OWT classes has been produced. These data have been used for sampling planning during the DOORS cruises.

Image: Example satellite data supplied for DOORS cruise support, both prior to the campaign (datasets such as composite dominant monthly optical water type as well as daily imagery for the 2 weeks leading up to the cruise) and while the ship was underway (example cruise support email images provided of chlorophyll-a and enhanced ocean colour) © DOORS

OWT represent bodies of water with spectrally distinct characteristics dependent upon in water concentrations of chlorophyll, suspended particulate matter and coloured dissolved organic matter. OWT classes can be utilized to design better performing water quality algorithms or estimating uncertainties, but they can further be used in their own right to characterize changes or seasonality in the Black Sea system.

The OWT data were generated to support the design of sampling campaigns across the Black Sea to maximise the representativity of the biogeo-optical variability. Using a novel method for assessing seasonality (MOVing Standard deviation Saturation - MOSS, approach described in Jönsson et al 2023), dominant timescales of seasonal turnover in optical variability as indicated by OWT classes for the Black Sea basin was assessed. Coastal waters regulated by freshwater inflow and climatic processes show a dominant timescale (τ_d) of variability of 2-5 months, which matches expectation of processes such as spring runoff. Other patterns such as the shorter timescales observed in the western Gyre as compared to the eastern Gyre, and τ_d values longer than a year at the northwest and southeast edges of the Black Sea Rim Current are currently being analysed further in conjunction with the wider consortium, in particular partners in WP5.

The OWT datasets are available in the DOORS SoS. The work on Optical Water Types and dominant timescales of variability was presented at the 2024 Ocean Science Meeting (ALSO/AGU/Oceanography Society), attended by close to 6,000 oceanographic researchers and industry representatives.

Image: Dominant timescales of variability (τ_d) in Optical Water Types across the Black Sea © DOORS

The ocean colour products in Black Sea including remote sensing reflectance (Rrs), Chlorophyll-a concentration (Chl-a), total suspended matter concentration (TSM), diffuse attenuation coefficient of downwelling irradiance at 490 nm (Kd(490)), backscattering coefficient at 443 nm (bbp(443)) from CMEMS OLCI, CMEMS MULTI sensor, CERTO OLCI and CERTO MSI products were validated using in situ measured biogeochemical and radiometric data. The in-situ data were compiled from two DOORS cruises in May and September 2023, CERTO project campaigns, CNR flow-through system, Institute of Oceanology (IO-BAS) national monitoring programme and bio-optical campaigns and three Aeronet-OC sites: Galata, Gloria and Section-7 in Black Sea.

Image: Overview of the in-situ data available from previous projects and collected during DOORS cruises for ocean colour product validation © DOORS

Remote sensing reflectance (R_{rs}) were measured using TriOS and Hyper-OCR radiometer, diffused attenuation coefficient of downwelling irradiance (K_d) were measured using Hyper-OCR, absorption and backscattering coefficients were collected using the optical cage. Water samples were collected and filtered through 47 μm pore size filters, and samples were analysed in the laboratory to measure Chlorophyll-a concentration (Chl-a) and total suspended matter (TSM). Satellite matchups were extracted from a 3x3 pixel window on the same day of in situ data collection for validation.

Results showed that the CERTO OLCI product yielded a significantly higher number of R_{rs} matchups than the CMEMS OLCI product due to the wider coverage by Polymer atmospheric correction. Both CMEMS and CERTO provide accurate R_{rs} values in visible bands from 490 nm to 665 nm with generally higher accuracy than other bands. The blended Chl-a algorithm used in CMEMS OLCI product presented accurate estimates, the optical water type (OWT) classification-based Chl-a algorithm in CERTO also provided accurate Chl-a estimates especially when Chl-a higher than 10 mg/m^3 , with slightly overestimation when Chl-a lower than 1 mg/m^3 .

Images: Comparison between in situ Chl-a and satellite-derived Chl-a from (a) CMEMS OLCI product using blended algorithm, (b) EUMETSAT product using NN algorithm, and (c) EUMETSAT product using OC4ME algorithm © DOORS

Images: Comparison between in situ Chl-a and satellite-derived Chl-a from CERTO (a) OLCI and (b) MSI products © DOORS

The CMEMS OLCI, CERTO OLCI and CERTO MSI provided acceptable TSM estimates with slightly underestimations. The CMEMS MULTI TSM product showed clear underestimations. Both CMEMS OLCI and MULTI provided accurate estimates for $K_d(490)$. The $b_{bp}(443)$ from CMEMS MULTI product showed clear underestimations.

The Copernicus CMEMS Ocean colour R_{rs} product showed overall good accuracy across the OLCI bands. The highest accuracy was at blue to green bands (490-560 nm) with a MAPE between 17-19%, and higher errors were observed in near-infrared bands (> 700nm). Chl-a product from CMEMS showed good consistency with in situ measured values although the MAPE is slightly high (76.6%). K_d at 490 nm from CMEMS product also showed good accuracy with a 20.6% MAPE. The TSM product showed slight lower accuracy of 100.80% MAPE.

Image: (a) Remote sensing reflectance measured from DOORS Black Sea cruise. Copernicus CMEMS ocean colour product validation for (b) Chl-a, (c) Kd at 490 nm, and (d) TSM in Black Sea © DOORS

Based on the validation work done, we recommend to the CMEMS OC- TAC to:

1. Include Polymer in the OLCI processing chain for Rrs retrieval, as it provides a wider spatial coverage than the EUMETSAT standard atmospheric correction, particularly for higher Chl-a, concentrations.
2. Assess whether the higher spatial coverage due to the change in atmospheric correction scheme occurs across the whole basin or only in the optically complex waters that are represented in the in-situ data compiled for this study.
3. Evaluate how to include the CERTO OWT blended algorithms for the higher Chl-a range within the current operational Chl-a, blending scheme algorithm that already includes two different regional algorithms exhibiting lower and higher optical complexity.
4. Assess whether the extended blending approach could be applied to both OLCI and the MULTI band-sets and thus the operational processing chains.

These data will be incorporated into the SoS and the bespoke Use Cases to demonstrate the value of the SoS in understanding the Black Sea and driving better practice in its management and support for the Blue Economy.

Modelling: Knowledge Gap Filling, Projection, Forecasting

DOORS provided an updated characterization of the environmental status of the Black Sea using state of the art open-source numerical modelling tools.

- Biogeochemical modelling allows the quantification of nutrient distribution at Black Sea scale to assess eutrophication.
- Lagrangian numerical studies confirmed that marine litter are widespread and persistent, posing significant risks to marine life and ecosystems. The numerical tools adopted in DOORS allow the identification of sources, distribution and evolution of marine litter across the Black Sea.

- Wave and storm surge modelling - at basin and coastal scale - provides data to quantify the effects of extreme events.
- Morphodynamic and flooding model outputs quantify the extent of storm effects and barrier beach modifications.

Model generated data allow for a high spatial and temporal coverage of the Black Sea and can be tailored to address specific topics of interest or threats by reproducing such processes and predict future conditions. There is a long history of using models in the Black Sea, but here the aim is to show the increased level of coordination among the different models applied in order to provide a consistent and as complete as possible picture of the Black Sea, trying to integrate and further improve the modelling capabilities. One focus is investigating the possible effects of the influx of water, sediments, nutrients and marine litter from the land to the sea via rivers.

The WAM model setup for the western Black Sea is designed to predict wave dynamics in near real time based on the high-resolution forecast wind data provided by ECMWF. The wind-wave model is integrated by HEREON and UPC with the morphodynamic model to predict the sediment transport rate and to estimate the erosion and flooding probability, especially for the upcoming extreme storm events. This result is of added value for coastal management and risk reduction. The operational model Kassandra, based on SHYFEM model, developed and operated by CNR, has been used for short-term wave and storm surge forecasting in both the Black Sea allowing very high resolution in the nearshore and to coastal areas. The SCHISM model setup of HEREON for the western Black Sea, using the river discharge provided by Deltares, will be further adapted to improve the prediction of circulation dynamics in the nearshore by HEREON, DELTARES, UPC.

Two highlights of the more general modelling effort developed in DOORS, which addressed also other threats relevant for the Black Sea (e.g. extreme events, changes in morphology, eutrophication, etc.) are here presented:

- The implementation of a Black Sea catchment model is providing updated information about the water, sediment and nutrients flux in all of the surrounding basins, including the 11 major rivers, for the first time;
- The implementation of a Lagrangian model is modelling the distribution of floating marine litter in the Black Sea and areas of accumulation from different riverine sources.

Image: Spatial extent of the Black Sea catchment model, including the Danube, Dniepr, and Dniestr rivers © DOORS

The catchment modelling makes use of the wflow_sbm open-source process-based distributed hydrology model (van Verseveld et al., 2021). Hydrological processes are represented on a regular fine grid of cells with their own physical characteristics (elevation, soil, land use and landcover). Meteorological forcing data are used to calculate the generation of runoff and infiltration, which is then routed through the catchment river system, taking into account the presence of natural lakes and reservoirs. The wflow framework also offers a component to calculate erosion and sediment delivery to the river network (Boisgontier and van Gils, 2020). Additional model components make use of the Delft3D-WAQ open-source water system modelling software (<https://oss.deltares.nl/web/delft3d>). These features are used for simulating nutrient emissions, representing different compartments of the techno-sphere (e.g. paved surfaces, wastewater and stormwater collection and treatment). The same software is used to represent in-stream processes for water temperature, fine sediment particles and nutrients (ICPR, 2014; Smits and van Beek, 2013).

Image: Catchment modelling: Simulated mean annual discharge (m³/s; top left), water temperature (°C; top right), total nitrogen (mg/L; bottom left) and suspended particulate matter concentration (mg/L; bottom right) for 11 rivers discharging to the Black Sea for the years 2011-2020 © DOORS

The Black Sea catchment models were prepared using global data to ensure consistency over the whole domain. With the wflow_sbm concept, after calibration, the simulated water flux represents well observations. The model could however be further improved by using regional or local precipitation. For some rivers, especially the Dniepr, the presence and operations of dams is a key point that is difficult to represent well with global data.

Image: (Left) Danube Freshwater inflow into the Black Sea (CNR) and Black Sea Phytoplankton Model (METU) © DOORS

The application of catchment modelling shows strong potential but also highlights several areas requiring further refinement:

- **Water Fluxes:** the presence and operation of dams is a key point. This affects the temporal distribution of river flows and evaporative losses.
- **Temperature Modelling:** the energy balances at below zero temperatures and the snowmelt hydrology are points of attention that affect the water temperatures in winter and spring.
- **Fine Sediment Modelling:** the representation of the river network morphology and the parameterization of settling and resuspension processes within such a representation is a complex point. Next to erosion and sediment delivery, this affects the temporal distribution of the particle concentration.
- **Nutrient Modelling:** This remains particularly challenging, requiring a balance between very detailed process-based approaches with high input data demands on one hand and semi-empirical methods that rely on local monitoring data on the other hand. A process-based method that connects the relevant socio-economic drivers (wastewater management, agriculture practices) to the emissions of nutrients to streams is evaluated.

The predicted nutrient emissions in the Danube River Basin were compared to recently published values and for most pathways show good agreement. The model performance for water temperature is also good. Similarly, the nitrogen concentration range is mostly well reproduced with a clear seasonal trend affected by, temperature influenced, denitrification losses. For suspended particulate matter the performance is reasonable. The concentration range and peak levels are well-reproduced, but the precise day-to-day dynamics are not always captured. As a substantial fraction of phosphorus is transported by sediments, the model performance is similar to that of the suspended particulate matter.

The dispersion of Floating Marine Litter (FML) in the marine environment is investigated through a LOCATE model configuration, which implements a CMEMS-WAM models results and OGS data in the Black Sea. Model results will support strategies for estimating clustering patterns, and strategies to combat marine litter pollution. **The coastal marine litter model, LOCATE**, utilises OceanParcels as a Lagrangian solver (Delandmeter & Van Sebille, 2019; Van Sebille et al., 2020). It integrates Eulerian hydrodynamic data and specializes in simulating litter motion and accumulation in coastal areas, adapting to nested grids of varying scales and resolutions. It includes modules like the beaching module.

Three scenarios were conducted: two involved homogeneous particle release, one considering Stokes Drift (SD), and the other excluding it (NSD). The third scenario involved particle release from nine main river basins.

Image: Graphical illustration of the simulation points used in the Black Sea particulate input scenarios. Left: Points every 18 km ca. for the simulation with homogeneous release. Right: Nine points with debris discharge from the main rivers of the Black Sea: Dnieper-Bug (DB), Dniester (DN), Danube (DA), Sakarya (S), Kizilirmak (K), Yesilirmak (Y), Çoruh (C), Rioni (R), and Don-Kuban (DK) © DOORS

Image: Distribution of accumulated particles by quadrants in 2017 simulations. Pie charts placed in SW, NW, SE, and NE quadrants. Colors denote origin: Dnieper-Bug (DB) in orange, Dniester (DN) in pink, Danube (DA) in magenta, Sakaraya (S) in purple, Kizilirmak (K) in lavender blue, Yesilirmak (Y) in blue, Coruh (C) in aquamarine green, Rioni (R) in green, and Don-Kuban (DK) in brown. Pie chart sizes proportional to percentages © DOORS

The southwest coast of the Black Sea showed a high Floating Marine Litter (FML) density in all scenarios, likely due to cyclonic circulation and substantial FML input from the Danube River and other northern rivers. Notably, factoring in Stokes Drift (SD) significantly affected particle residence time in offshore waters and the percentage washing ashore. Incorporating SD raised the beached particle percentage from 45.5% to 75.5% and decreased the average residence time from 99 to 63 days. These findings support recent literature highlighting the need to consider Stokes drift to prevent overestimating residence times.

The marine litter model has provided valuable insights into Floating Marine Litter (FML) accumulation patterns in the Black Sea. Two key high-density areas were identified: the eastern region near the Georgian coast and the northwestern Black Sea - both consistent with observational data. This research emphasizes the importance of incorporating Stokes drift into FML transport models, particularly for understanding litter accumulation and its impact on coastal environments.

Looking ahead, future work will focus on integrating catchment modelling with marine litter transport modelling to support a more holistic understanding of litter dynamics from source to sea. Our goal is to further develop the ongoing modelling effort beyond the state of the art, to better address the main challenges in the area. Thereby making a broad use of the added information directly coming from the DOORS project.

Understanding Change: Use Case Demonstrators for the SoS

Quantifying natural and anthropogenic coastal change

New data products were developed on Black Sea coastal dynamics in DOORS, using a combined Sentinel 1 SAR and Sentinel 2 MSI approach validated with in situ data.

Sentinel-1 SAR images and Sentinel-2 MSI images with a spatial resolution of 20 m from 2016 to 2023 were used to detect the coast dynamics in Black Sea. The method developed can combine the information observed from SAR and optical images to detect the coast dynamics, and used in situ measured coastlines from Romania and Georgia to validate the results.

Validation results showed that the method developed can detect accurate coastline from satellite images with an uncertainty of 11.8 m, which is half of a satellite image pixel. The detected coast dynamics from satellite images also agreed well with changes observed from in-situ data.

Image: Difference between satellite-derived coastline and in situ measured coastline in Romania and Georgia © DOORS

Application of the developed method to the whole Black Sea showed that there are 48.0 km² coastal area changes, including natural process (erosion and accretion), human interventions (construction of harbours, airports). The majority changes were observed in Danube delta (Romania and Ukraine), river mouths in Turkey (e.g., Kizilirmak River), and river mouths in Georgia (e.g., Rioni River mouth, Kodori River mouth).

Of the 35.1 km² of coastal change observed in the Black Sea:

- 43.3 % (15.2 km²) of the changes occurred in the Turkish coast
- 72.5 % of which are artificial associated with coast engineering
- 91 % of all the artificial changes in the Black Sea coast

Image: Coast dynamics during 2016 and 2023 observed in Black from satellite images: Natural Change (Left) and Anthropogenic Change (Right) © DOORS

Image: Coastal Sediment Dynamics (including erosion and accretion), Danube Delta, Romania (Sentinel 1 SAR and Sentinel 2 MSI Data) © DOORS

Image: Coastal Sediment Dynamics (including erosion and accretion), Georgia (Sentinel 1 SAR and Sentinel 2 MSI Data) © DOORS

Evaluation of marine litter distribution, origin and area of accumulation

The quantification of microplastics from space is one of the milestones for the SoS’s contribution to monitoring capability. **For the first time ever in the Black Sea**, a methodology has been implemented for the validation of marine debris modelling and marine litter mapping. This methodology implements the use of Sentinel-1 SAR imagery for viewing surfactants within the Black Sea. Surfactants can be used as tracers for marine plastic pollution, and will also follow the similar currents that marine debris does. Copernicus ERA5 wind speed data and CMEMS chlorophyll-a -products have been utilised for aiding surfactant identification and validating if they are of biogenic algal origin. In the study DOORS researchers carried out with this purpose, across all Sentinel-1 images in 2017, there were 320 instances of surfactants visible in Maximum Accumulation Zones and 144 instances within Minimum Accumulation Zones:

Image: Mapping marine litter using Sentinel-1 SAR data: Left: Points of maximum accumulation and minimal accumulation zones – zones determined by UPC and HEREON. Right: Focused view of MaxZone5, pink square NW Türkiye, with visible surfactants on the surface waters. Wind speeds - 2.63 m/s. Chl-a concentration – 1.26mg/m3. Image Acquired December 4th 2017 © DOORS

Overall, it has been found that surfactants are visible with double the number of instances found within the maximum accumulation zones modelled by Castro-Romero et al, 2023, and Stanev & Ricker, 2019, when compared with the minimum accumulation zones.

From the DOORS System of Systems to a Digital Twin (DT) for the Black Sea

The next evolution of the System of System’s capability should be in the development of a Digital Twin of the Black Sea, an adaptive, interactive model that mimics the structure, context and behaviour of the Black Sea through real-time data integration.

Building for the Future of the Black Sea:

Image: Digital Twin of the Black Sea architecture © DOORS

Image: DOORS & BRIDGE-BS: Delivering a Federation of DTs © DOORS, BRIDGE-BS

A Digital Twin is more than a static model; it is a digital replica of a natural, engineered, or socio-environmental system that continuously evolves. It fuses high-resolution models with real-time data flows from distributed sensors and observation systems, enabling a constant feedback loop between the physical and digital realms. This two-way interaction allows the virtual model to not only reflect current states but also respond, adapt, and predict future scenarios.

Built on this foundation, the Digital Twin of the Black Sea would:

- Support real-time monitoring and forecasting of key environmental parameters
- Enable “what-if” scenario simulations, testing potential outcomes of policy or environmental interventions
- Enhance understanding of complex, interlinked processes such as water circulation, pollution transport, ecosystem dynamics, and socio-economic drivers
- Deliver insights that inform decision-making across multiple sectors, from marine spatial planning to fisheries management and climate resilience

In an era marked by rising uncertainty and rapid environmental change, Digital Twins represent a transformative leap forward. They foster greater creativity, resilience, and agility in planning and governance by providing a testbed for innovation and optioneering - the exploration and evaluation of multiple intervention strategies. Far from being a trend, Digital Twins are becoming an essential infrastructure for evidence-based decision-making and systemic adaptation. The Black Sea Digital Twin will not only accelerate scientific discovery but also deliver tangible financial, environmental, and socio-economic benefits, aligning with the broader goals of sustainability and inclusive growth.

Reimagining how we conceptualize and interact with the environment:

- Transforming Environmental Understanding. A DT enables us to reimagine environmental systems not as static or isolated, but as dynamic, interconnected networks. It supports a systemic view that integrates ecological, hydrological, atmospheric, and human dimensions—providing a truly holistic perspective.
- Redefining Virtual Engagement. The DT allows users—from scientists to policymakers and citizens—to interact with virtual models in intuitive, immersive ways, using real-time data to explore scenarios and visualize impacts like never before.
- A Safe Space for Experimentation. Through simulation of real-world interventions in a risk-free digital environment, the DT enables real-time exploration of policy and management options. It helps assess not only expected outcomes, but also unintended consequences, allowing for adaptive, informed responses.
- Enabling a Systems Approach. The DT facilitates a multi-dimensional understanding by embedding social, political, economic, and cultural values into the modelling process. It becomes a shared platform for dialogue and decision-making across disciplines and sectors.
- Balancing Competing Objectives. By integrating diverse datasets and stakeholder perspectives, the DT supports trade-off analysis and conflict resolution, particularly in areas where priorities may compete—such as climate adaptation, biodiversity protection, and Blue Economy development.

The value of a Black Sea Digital Twin lies in its ability to offer the spatial and temporal resolution needed to address the region’s most pressing issues. Some key applications include:

- **Climate Adaptation Strategy Development.** Explore and compare ("optioneer") a range of climate adaptation measures, tailored to local vulnerabilities and community needs.
- **Managing and Mitigating - extreme/shock/security events.** Respond to extreme events, such as pollution spills, marine heatwaves, or geopolitical disruptions, with agility and foresight.
- **Coastal Zone Planning.** Guide sustainable development in sectors like renewable energy, aquaculture, and maritime transport - balancing growth with environmental integrity.

- **Navigation and Infrastructure Optimization.** Improve operations and safety in ports and harbours, supporting efficient, low-impact maritime logistics.
- **Addressing Coastal Erosion.** Model erosion dynamics and assess implications for coastal communities, informing strategies to protect both livelihoods and ecosystems.

Further on, the Digital Earth, as described by the European Commission, is *“an interactive digital replica of the entire planet that can facilitate a shared understanding of the multiple relationships between the physical and natural environments and society.”* It goes beyond traditional models by integrating real-time data, dynamic simulation, and interactive visualization to create a living, learning system—one that evolves with both scientific discovery and societal needs. This vision lays the foundation for the next generation of Digital Twins (DTs): not just high-fidelity models, but fully integrated platforms that support interactive exploration, decision-making, and collaborative action.

The European Space Agency (ESA) is a key enabler of this transformation through its Digital Twin Earth precursors, which provide critical infrastructure and innovation across diverse domains. These include Data Cubes and Foundational Models for:

- Forest ecosystems
- Hydrology and water resources
- Antarctica’s evolving cryosphere
- Global food systems
- Ocean dynamics
- Climate hot spots and vulnerability zones

These efforts serve as modular building blocks for the Digital Earth, offering consistent, harmonized, and time-resolved Earth observation data that feed into dynamic models and interactive interfaces. ESA’s flagship initiative, Destination Earth, further accelerates this vision with the development of a 5 km-resolution Climate Digital Twin of the entire planet. This high-performance simulation environment supports:

- Modelling of wind energy potential, river flows, hydrometeorological events, and urban heat stress
- Scenario testing for climate resilience and sustainable development
- Integration with real-world applications at regional and local scales

The future of Digital Earth will be driven by convergence across multiple frontiers:

- **Advanced Sensing:** Including the detection of complex pollutants and fine-scale environmental variability
- **Earth Observation Innovations:** Enhanced frequency, spatial resolution, and data volume from new satellite missions
- **Next-Gen Modelling Approaches,** such as: AI and Machine Learning to unlock patterns and automate forecasting; Physics-based models for accuracy and credibility; Hybrid approaches combining empirical insights with theoretical rigor
- **Uncertainty Quantification:** Essential for responsible and confident decision-making
- **Human-Centric Interfaces:** Real-time, interactive tools that connect users—scientists, policymakers, businesses, and citizens—to a shared, dynamic understanding of the Earth system

The development of a Digital Twin for the Black Sea aligns with ESA’s broader Digital Earth agenda. It represents a regional implementation of global capability, tailored to specific socio-environmental challenges such as: Climate adaptation and coastal resilience; Marine litter and pollution tracking; Ecosystem protection and sustainable Blue Economy development.

2. Focus on Blue Growth Accelerator (BGA)

The Blue Economy represents a sustainable approach to using ocean resources for economic gain while safeguarding the health of our oceans. It involves various industries like fishing, shipping, renewable energy, and tourism, aiming to create prosperity while ensuring the long-term health of marine ecosystems. This approach values innovation, responsible practices, and new opportunities that benefit businesses while preserving the natural wealth of our oceans. It’s about finding a balance where economic growth aligns with environmental sustainability, recognizing the immense potential of our oceans to support thriving businesses in a way that protects our planet for generations to come. We regard the Blue Economy sustainable if it will not add to a further exceeding of our planetary boundaries. Thus, coastal and marine, natural resources across the Black Sea should be exploited carefully and environmental protection should be ensured. Sustainability also encompasses the notion that the exploitation of a natural resource to the benefit of one user, may hamper other users and should therefore be discussed with them.

Black Sea Ecosystem Services (ES)

Black Sea Ecosystem Services		Black Sea ecosystem types			
		Marine inlets & transitional waters	Coastal areas	Shelf	Open oceans
PROVISIONING	Fisheries	Score 4	3	2	1
		S.D. 1.3	1.9	2.0	1.6
	Aquaculture	Score 3	3	1	0
		S.D. 1.6	2.0	1.7	0.8
	Water	Score 3	1	0	0
		S.D. 2.0	1.7	1.1	0.8
	Timber	Score 1	1	0	0
		S.D. 1.7	1.7	1.2	1.1
	Edible plant and animal species	Score 2	2	2	0
		S.D. 1.7	2.0	2.1	1.7
Commercial resources	Score 4	3	2	0	
	S.D. 1.5	1.8	2.1	2.2	
Renewable energy	Score 4	4	3	0	
	S.D. 1.5	1.7	2.0	3.2	
REGULATING	Air quality	Score 4	4	4	3
		S.D. 0.9	1.5	1.7	1.8
	Erosion control	Score 4	3	1	0
		S.D. 0.9	1.4	1.7	1.1
	Flood protection	Score 3	2	1	0
		S.D. 1.6	1.6	1.4	1.3
	Local climatic regulation	Score 4	4	3	3
		S.D. 0.9	1.4	1.5	1.7
	Water quality/waste regulation	Score 4	3	0	0
		S.D. 1.4	1.6	3.3	2.9
Nutrient cycling	Score 4	3	3	0	
	S.D. 1.3	1.7	1.7	3.3	
Species distribution and complexity	Score 3	2	2	1	
	S.D. 1.4	1.7	1.8	1.3	
Global climatic regulation	Score 3	3	2	2	
	S.D. 1.6	1.9	1.7	1.9	
CULTURAL	Recreation	Score 4	4	2	1
		S.D. 0.8	1.4	1.8	1.5
	Tourism	Score 5	4	3	0
		S.D. 0.7	1.4	1.8	2.5
Aesthetic values	Score 4	4	3	2	
	S.D. 0.9	1.4	1.7	2.0	
Cultural, historical, religious and identity values	Score 5	4	3	3	
	S.D. 0.6	1.4	1.8	2.1	

* Score:

0	No relevant capacity of the ecosystem to provide the ecosystem service
1	Very low relevant capacity of the ecosystem to provide the ecosystem service
2	Low relevant capacity of the ecosystem to provide the ecosystem service
3	Moderate relevant capacity of the ecosystem to provide the ecosystem service
4	High relevant capacity of the ecosystem to provide the ecosystem service
5	Very high relevant capacity of the ecosystem to provide the ecosystem service

DOORS has been a pioneer in the mapping of the Black Sea Ecosystem Services analysis by using the ES matrix approach and the World Resources Institute (WRI) corporate ES review method. Based on that, we analysed unused or underused ES of the Black Sea.

This approach revealed two economic activities with potential for sustainable growth:

- biotechnology and
- off-shore wind energy (where the risks and opportunity analysis identified possible key impacts (positive and negative)).

To further and sustainably develop the offshore wind energy in the Black Sea, we presented targeted recommendations for researchers and governmental stakeholders, addressing critical areas such as regulatory frameworks, environmental assessments, stakeholder engagement, and cross-border cooperation.

DOORS also developed its own sustainable Blue Growth indicators. Five core principles we developed for a sustainable Blue Economy:

1. Avoid overexploitation the Black Sea’s natural resources

2. Do not litter or pollute the Black Sea coast and rivers
3. Minimize waste production (reduce, reuse, recycle)
4. Minimize carbon footprint (help reducing climate change)
5. Be mindful that one Blue Growth sector may hinder another

Innovation Pathways: Guiding Sustainable Blue Economy Development

DOORS offered a vision for how Blue Economy should be developed by 2050. This is why Innovation pathways were developed as a structured approach to identify key milestones for the long-term advancement of Blue Economy. This work was done together with stakeholders from all countries, who mapped the road to be taken towards the Vision implementation and relevant milestones along this way. Through facilitated discussions, key Blue Economy sectors were prioritized, and critical environmental, socioeconomic, and policy challenges were identified at both national and regional levels.

Building on this, DOORS has a major role in opening the path towards the development of the Blue Economy in the Black Sea, via the Blue Growth Accelerator. This is achieved by:

- identifying Black Sea opportunities for sustainable Blue Economy and the (potential) entrepreneurs who can exploit them;
- enabling these entrepreneurs to exploit these opportunities by training / provision of professional support and facilitating their access to funding and investment opportunities; and
- fostering collaboration between academia and the industry and, as an added benefit, promoting the entrepreneurial culture and increasing capacity for blue innovation.

The Black Sea Accelerator (BSA) Initiative

In collaboration with the H2020 BRIDGE-BS, the Black Sea Accelerator (BSA) initiative was set up, aligned with the Black Sea Common Maritime Agenda and supporting the practical implementation of the BS SRIA Pillar 2 Black Sea Blue Economy.

An [open call for expressions of interest](#) was launched in June 2023, inviting:

- startups, Small or Medium size Enterprises (SMEs), universities or other organisations and individuals
- entities based in the Black Sea region and beyond (but with an interest in expanding their entrepreneurial activity in the region)
- innovative solutions in the following blue economy sectors: Observation and monitoring, Ports, Transport & Logistics (shipbuilding and repair), Fisheries & Aquaculture, Tourism and recreational activities, Blue-biotechnology and related products, Sustainable and renewable marine energy, Nature-based services/solutions (coastal/marine)
- Sustainable solutions of Technology Readiness Level (TRL): 4-9.

A dedicated online event, co-organised by DOORS and BRIDGE-BS, was hosted on 03/07/2023 to present the BSA call and the services to be offered. The event attracted around 100 participants and was further promoted by BlueInvest, through the guest speaker from the initiative.

Image: [The Black Sea Accelerator brochure](#) providing more information about the Blue Economy opportunities in specific sectors of the Black Sea region and details of the services we offered to participants © DOORS

Unlocking a wave of opportunities for the Black Sea Blue Economy pioneers, the BSA provided a gateway to resources, mentorship, and networking in Blue Economy sectors. The program is strategically aligned with Key sectors of the Blue Economy:

1. Ocean Observation
2. Ports & Transport
3. Fisheries and Aquaculture
4. Marine Tourism
5. Blue Biotechnology
6. Renewable Energy
7. Nature-based Solutions.

Through the open call, the BSA welcomed:

- ✓ 22 Startups with Innovative ideas.
- ✓ Over 25 applications received, showcasing a robust response to BSA initiative. Innovations in Blue Economy sectors Key focus areas included aquaculture (7 applications), blue biotechnology (6 applications), marine Renewable Energy (4 applications) and transport (5 applications).
- ✓ Applicants from 6 Black Sea countries and in addition 4 more application from non-regional applicants, aiming to broaden their entrepreneurial ventures into this area.
- ✓ 64% of the startups were at TRL 4-6, while 36% of them were at TRL 7-9.

The Black Sea Accelerator provided a platform for participants to collaborate, learn, and grow their ventures by offering tailored training, mentorship, networking opportunities, and access to resources and funding. Whether they were looking to launch a new venture, scale an existing business, or develop innovative solutions to pressing challenges, the accelerator program equipped participants with the knowledge, skills, and support they need to succeed in the Blue Economy sector and make a positive impact in the Black Sea region.

This initiative facilitated the seamless exploitation and exchange of DOORS research results. It went beyond conventional paradigms, generating a wave of ideas and fostering the emergence of innovative start-ups.

Image: Overview on the Black Sea Accelerator participants © DOORS

All Accelerator participants gained tailored mentoring, networking opportunities, and direct investor connections through the [DOORS matchmaking platform](https://www.doorsblacksea.eu/matchmakingplatform). (<https://www.doorsblacksea.eu/matchmakingplatform>).

Through our online training sessions, startups had the opportunity to receive feedback from expert evaluators, allowing them to refine and enhance their strategies and solutions. We helped businesses demonstrating a workable and scalable business model and supported them in the process of presenting their products to external investors. Follow up sessions were scheduled after each training, where applicants were tasked with assignments (developing their own business model, completing the SWOT analysis of their venture and discuss it with business consultants from KANTOR, preparing their 1-minute pitch); could be discussed them with the trainers and receive feedback, in 1-1 dedicated sessions.

Completed trainings:	Responsible partner	Learning objective
From Concept to Execution: Business Model Fundamentals (March 2024, facilitated by DOORS and BRIDGE-BS)	ATHENA RC and BRIDGE- BS expert	Utilise the Canvas Business Model framework to map out key components of business models, including value proposition, customer segments, revenue streams, and resource loops
Strategic Insights: Mastering Business Planning Essentials (April 2024, facilitated by DOORS)	KANTOR	Understand the fundamental components of a business plan and its importance in the entrepreneurial process.
The Power of the Pitch: Strategies for Effective Communication (April 2024, facilitated by DOORS and BRIDGE-BS)	ATHENA RC and BRIDGE-BS expert	Gain an understanding of the structure and components of an effective pitch. Learn techniques for crafting a compelling elevator pitch.

Circular business models and Evaluation of sustainable performance (June 2024, facilitated by DOORS)	ATHENA RC	Understand the principles and importance of circular economy concepts in the context of business development. Guide participants through the process of applying circular economy principles to develop their own innovative and circular business models
How do startups attract personnel? / How to prepare a "winning" investment presentation (June 2024, facilitated by DOORS)	KANTOR	HR Training: Identify the key traits and skills necessary for startup roles. Learn effective strategies for attracting and recruiting top talent. "Winning" Investment presentation training: Understand the components that contribute to a strong and persuasive investor presentation. Learn techniques for integrating visual aids into presentations to clarify and emphasize key points.
Mastering DOORS SoS data services (July 2024, facilitated by DOORS)	Brockmann Consult, IO-BAS, USTIR	Operate DOORS Data viewers. Browse the catalogue, view and extract data and use this data in their own applications in connection with the relevant BGA application.
Financials for startups (September 2024, facilitated by DOORS)	KANTOR	Develop comprehensive financial models to forecast revenues, expenses, and cash flows, enabling startups to make informed financial decisions and effectively present their financial strategies to investors.

All the trainings are available as Life-Long Training resources on the DOORS website, under the [Tools for Business](#). LifeWatch ERIC provided technical support to the delivery and dissemination of the BSA. A dedicated section on the LifeWatch ERIC training platform was created under [International Projects - DOORS](#) to host the recordings, presentations and other materials produced by the BSA programme. This solution ensures long term sustainability of the content even after the project ends.

Recognizing our impact in fostering innovation in the Black Sea, we have, proudly, received:

- 🚩 The 'Best Project Winner 2024' in the Category "Competitive, Innovative and Sustainable Blue Economy for the Black Sea", at the 2024 Annual Conference of the Common Maritime Agenda community (Black Sea countries + EC - DG MARE)
- 🚩 An 'Honourable Mention' for the BSA, for its role in driving investment CMA stakeholder conference (Moldova 2024) - category "supporting investment in the Black Sea"

Blue Career Guide: Unlocking Opportunities in the Black Sea Blue Economy

The *Blue Career Guide* is a comprehensive resource for individuals aiming to start or grow a sustainable career in the Blue Economy — industries relying on ocean and marine resources, such as sustainable fisheries,

marine energy, tourism, biotechnology, aquaculture, and conservation. As global focus on ocean sustainability and climate action rises, so does the demand for skilled professionals.

Key sections of the guide include:

- **Understanding the Blue Economy:** An overview of its sectors and role in promoting sustainable growth and innovation.
- **Career Pathways:** Various job opportunities, from marine science to environmental advocacy.
- **Skills and Qualifications:** Essential education, technical expertise, and soft skills needed.
- **Opportunities for Growth:** Trends and innovations like renewable marine energy and conservation technologies, with advice on aligning careers to high-growth areas.
- **Navigating the Job Market:** Practical tips for job searching, networking, and resume building.
- **Expert Advice:** Interviews with Blue Economy professionals from the Black Sea region sharing real-world insights and career tips.

DOORS Blue Career Guide highlights key growth sectors within the Blue Economy, including marine tourism, fisheries, renewable energy, aquaculture, and shipbuilding. These sectors are rapidly expanding and present significant opportunities for sustainable development and employment across coastal and marine regions. The guide identifies critical gaps in workforce skills, underlining the urgent need to align educational and training programmes with industry demands. It provides clear recommendations for academic and vocational pathways that can prepare the next generation of professionals to thrive in the maritime sector.

A central message of the guide is the importance of regional cooperation in boosting employment and fostering innovation within the Blue Economy. Strengthening vocational training systems, establishing dedicated Blue Economy career portals, and enhancing job-market linkages are key steps recommended to address these challenges and unlock the full potential of the sector.

The Black Sea Special Interest Group (SIG)

The Black Sea Special Interest Group is a key component of the DOORS project. It brings together a focused group working to champion the opportunities presented by the blue economy on and around the Black Sea. Established in October 2023 and launched formally in September 2024, the Special Interest Group developed a package of work to raise the profile of the Blue Economy across the Black Sea region, culminating in a [Portfolio of Investment Opportunities](#) that offer a new direction for economic growth for the region’s people and communities.

Images: The SIG Booklet © DOORS

The Group is chaired by international development leader and UK Parliamentarian Jack McConnell. Membership also includes former Bulgarian Minister for Foreign Affairs Nadezhda Neynsky, former NATO

Secretary General George Robertson, and Galina Teleuca, Deputy Mayor of Jurilovca on Romania's Black Sea coast. They are complemented by Professor Adrian Stanica (Director, GeoEcoMar, Romania); Professor Andrew Tyler (Scotland Hydro Nation Chair, University of Stirling, UK), Dr. Vangelis Papathanassiou (GeoEcoMar); Chris Freaan (Head of Economic Diplomacy, British Embassy, Bucharest); Professor Joe Little (Entrepreneur in Residence, University of Stirling); Linsey Dickson (Interim Executive Director of Research, Innovation and Business Engagement, University of Stirling); and Professor Malcolm MacLeod (Senior Deputy Principal, University of Stirling). The SIG's business management and external affairs were led by Matt Francis (Public Affairs Manager, University of Stirling).

SIG's focus is structured around four (4) headline themes:

1. Digital Innovation. State of the art technology allows an appreciation of the entire Black Sea like never before, increasing awareness of the Sea's fragility, and enabling novel solutions and policy approaches to be considered. This digital capability is the foundation of an exciting range of innovations, from AI education tools to navigational aids.
2. Aquaculture. Aquaculture is one of the world's fastest-growing sectors. The Black Sea has a nascent aquaculture industry, with scope for expansion, but the diversity of the Black Sea's coastline requires close attention to the siting and setup of any marine aquaculture facility. There is appetite from regional industry to exploit this potential, and significant market potential in the region for farmed produce, particularly in Romania and Bulgaria. Further potential exists for the export of high-value, high-quality species to the international market.
3. Tourism, Heritage and Leisure. The Black Sea and its shores enjoy a rich cultural heritage, from classical civilisations to the legacies of twentieth century conflict. Novel technologies offer exciting opportunities to reinterpret the region's history, allowing communities to tell stories about their own past, present and future. Mass tourism has a footprint on some parts of the Black Sea coast, while wildlife tourism is established in Romania's Danube Delta; there is potential to respond to the growing demand for sustainable tourism by offering localised, low environmental impact experiences, and supporting infrastructure. Coupled with a focus on local, artisan producers of food and drink, a more targeted and sustainable tourist offer that celebrates the best of the region's culture is ripe for exploration.
4. Circular Economy. Three decades after near-ecological collapse, the Black Sea is undergoing a fragile rehabilitation. However, this recovery is threatened by new challenges, including climate change. Like everywhere else in the world, Black Sea states must find new solutions to meeting demands for both energy and international climate obligations. These pressures create new opportunities to develop a circular economy, seizing the potential created by emerging technologies to tackle localised problems from pollution and marine litter, through to larger scale strategic considerations including energy security and global trade.

Across seven (7) meetings, The SIG explored, identified and triaged more than 20 potential blue economy opportunities, from major, international organisations with potential to develop a footprint in the region, through to home-grown entrepreneurs with potential to upscale, given appropriate support. A significant source of prospects was the DOORS Blue Economy Accelerator, which provided numerous leads across the SIG's key themes. SIG member Joe Little harnessed additional prospects and contacts through his networks in the marine and ocean technology sector.

With input from Eleni Manousiadi, the SIG assessed these prospects according to their scale, maturity and readiness to be presented to investors. Those prospects that met the SIG's criteria were included in the final Investment Portfolio.

On 22 February 2025, a high-impact stakeholder event was held at in central London, developed and led by the SIG. The event served as early networking opportunity between seven (7) select prospects identified by the SIG, with a targeted, hand-picked and invite-only selection of nine (9) investors and associates, primarily based in the City of London. This included representatives of Venture Capital and Asset Management firms, together with representatives from the energy sector including IPIECA and OMV Petrom.

Image: SIG Chair Lord McConnell opens the SIG London investor showcase event, London, UK, 25 February 2025

The crescendo of the SIG’s activities was the launch of Blue Economy Investment Portfolio on 15 April 2025, at the Residence of the British Ambassador, in Bucharest. This was a high-level occasion, attended by an audience of 70 investors and diplomats, which celebrated the immense potential for blue growth on and around the Black Sea, exemplified by the diverse and innovative prospects included in the Portfolio. The transformational nature of these prospects and the importance of raising the profile of the Black Sea in a turbulent regional geopolitical context was also recognised.

In addition to more than ten (10) ambassadors and senior diplomats, more than 35 investors and representatives from the business, finance and philanthropic sectors attended, including representation from CitiBank, Rothschilds’ Bank, the Black Sea Trust, Cincinnatus Capital Group, the Schmidt Foundation, OMV Petrom, the National Bank of Romania, and the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development. Additionally, a handful of deputies and senators from the Parliament of Romania attended, along with senior civil servants and ministerial advisors – which was an opportunity to reiterate the importance of the Black Sea and the blue economy to this important, influential audience.

The launch event included a further showcase of eight (8) investment prospects and opportunities, together with high-level contributions from Dr Rebeccah Shah (Chargée d’Affairs, British Embassy); Dr Adrian Stanica (DOORS Project Co-Ordinator) and Lord Jack McConnell (University of Stirling Chancellor, and SIG chair). Several promising leads from the event are being pursued.

Image, L-R: SIG Chair Lord Jack McConnell; Dr. Rebeccah Shah (Chargée d’Affairs, British Embassy Bucharest) and Prof. Adrian Stanica, DOORS Project Coordinator), holding the DOORS Black Sea Blue Economy Investment Portfolio at the launch event, Bucharest, 15 April 2025

3. Focus on Knowledge Transfer and Training (KTT)

KTT built upon on existing, and developed new collaborations between the different actors on science and policy to promote a culture of openness, share best practice and knowledge.

DOORS partners assessed the existing capabilities of Black Sea educational and research institutions to establish professional programs that can stimulate and invigorate Blue Economy sectors in the region. This assessment served as the foundation for training exercises – for young researchers, students and other categories of interested persons have also been run through our Early-Stage Researcher Exchange (ESRE) program, Mutual Mobilisation Learning (MMLs) workshops series across the Black Sea (two rounds - in Bulgaria, Georgia, Moldova, Türkiye, Ukraine), Lifelong online training courses and learning materials (designed for vocational learners) and finally the Train the Trainers (TtT) event. A pathway was built for a Black Sea MSc Programme (in which any Black Sea country university can take and implement), and its implementation as an Erasmus Mundus MSc.

Pan-European approaches had to be tailored to Black Sea realities and lessons learned were made publicly available. The approaches deployed in DOORS build innovation communities, connect national, regional and international experts in different disciplines, promote shared learning and innovation, and establish the foundations of collaborative research and innovation.

The DOORS project has actively fostered Ocean Literacy and Citizen Science to bridge the gap between scientific research, policy, and public engagement, as well as to enhance public involvement in marine stewardship. Through our DOORS Ocean Literacy Network, carrying out workshops and citizen science activities across the Black Sea, we have enabled coastal communities and youth to better understand and contribute to the sustainable management of Black Sea ecosystems. Informed citizens and engaged local actors will drive more sustainable coastal and marine practices, enhance environmental monitoring efforts, and support data-driven decision-making. Ultimately, these actions will foster a stronger culture of marine conservation, innovation, and economic resilience for the Black Sea region.

Mutual Mobilisation (MML) Workshops: Learning together to seek solutions

Mutual Mobilisation (MML) workshops provided platforms for regional and local stakeholders, such as regional and local authorities, businesses, civil society, and stakeholders involved in Responsible Research and Innovation, to explore issues together and express their perspectives and collaboratively learn. We completed two rounds of workshops conducted across the Black Sea region, held in Romania, Ukraine, Moldova, Türkiye, Georgia, and Bulgaria. These workshops engaged over 300 representatives with broad representation across the range of Black Sea Blue Economy sectors.

The goal of the workshops was to bring together experts and users of marine products, to raise awareness and share knowledge and enhance skills. Sessions included plenary expert talks, round table discussions and hand-on practical exercises to explore an effective pan-European marine data infrastructure. During the Mutual Mobilization Learning (MML) workshop, attendees from partner countries were introduced to various tools aimed at enhancing access to databases relevant to Research and Innovation (RI): DOORS mapping tool, SeaDataNet, COPERNICUS, EMODNET, MarineLitterWatch, EMSO-EUXINUS Network, EURO-ARGO Eric, Global Fishing Watch, MEPA Atlas, LifeWatch Eric, OceanOPS, Danubius RI, EO Browser, Marine Analyst, Eurofleets+, JERICO RI, etc.

Through interactive training and collaborative activities, we aimed to ensure that Research Infrastructure

services in the Black Sea region meet the needs of both present and future generations. Additionally, we aimed to provide training for researchers and businesses on utilizing various services, tools, and data available, including those from EU initiatives like EMODnet, SeaDataNet, Euro-Argo Eric, Copernicus, as well as our own System of Systems (SoS). By doing so, we are empowering them to maximize the potential of existing data and monitoring efforts, contributing to the growth of the Blue Economy and informing political decisions in the region. We brought along the lessons we have learned, the bonds we have formed, and a mutual dedication to utilising the SoS and other data aggregation services for the betterment of the Black Sea region as a whole.

Equipping tomorrow’s Black Sea society: Developing Professional Programmes

DOORS partners further afield are developing an MSc. programme that capitalises on the uniqueness of the Black Sea. The two-tiered programme covers, in many aspects, key thematic areas such as the Black Sea’s ecosystems, history, oceanography, geomorphology, enclosed basin characteristics, geopolitics, political transformation and policy diversity.

The output will be a comprehensive MSc. proposal that can be adopted by universities across Black Sea countries, with a clear pathway toward its transformation into an Erasmus Mundus MSc. programme. This pathway involves the establishment of micro-credentials, the development of Blended Intensive Programmes (BIPs), and the coordination of strategic activities to build university alliances and formal cooperation agreements. These foundational steps are designed to ensure academic excellence, cross-border collaboration, and the long-term sustainability of the MSc. programme within the Erasmus+ framework.

Image: DOORS pathway towards a DOORS-powered Erasmus Mundus MSc. Programme © DOORS

Multi-Actor Fora (MAFs): Deep diving into community concerns

Multi-Actor Fora (MAFs) are also employed in DOORS as a unique type of stakeholder engagement framework. MAFs brought together national stakeholders from Bulgaria, Georgia, Moldova, Romania, Türkiye, and Ukraine, with varied backgrounds, to assist scientists in prioritising Black Sea issues, with an emphasis on Blue Economy sectors and policies, as well as the deployment of innovations to address identified gaps. From November 2022 to April 2024, 10 workshops were implemented in the 6 Black Sea countries, bringing together more than 160 key players interested in the Black Sea’s Blue Economy. Discussions mapped national Blue Economy contexts, reviewed and prioritised contexts in terms of development, reviewed the working vision for the Black Sea, reviewed preliminary innovation pathways, and set milestones to achieve the stakeholder’s vision for the Black Sea.

During the first round *Capture Fisheries, Marine & Coastal Tourism, Marine R&D, Shipping/Ports, Marine aquaculture, Ocean Renewable Energy, Marine Transport, Shipbuilding, Marine Business Services, Safety & Surveillance, Offshore wind energy, and Offshore oil & gas* were identified by the participants as the most important Blue Economy sectors for the Black Sea. The workshops identified also major challenges in political, environmental, social, technological, legal, and economic areas that need to be overcome for a successful implementation.

The second round focused on reviewing the long-term working vision for the Black Sea and preliminary innovation pathways requested to transform the vision into reality. 26 Innovation Pathways were developed for each Sector individually for each country, taking into account factors such as technical advancements, societal trends, regulatory changes, and economic growth - as well as setting milestones for achieving the vision in each relevant sector using the Future Radars tool to map relevant innovations from the BGA onto each of these milestones.

This process does not only drive awareness but also enhances the development of SoS and capacity-building initiatives essential for the blue economy’s sustainable advancement.

In this short clip, Lydia Papadaki of Athena RC in Greece explains about how our Multi-Actor Fora (MAFs) represent a systematic approach to stakeholder engagement in DOORS, providing that all important link between science and societal experience: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1hshk_CSqiQ

Enhancing next-gen professional networks: The Early-Stage Researcher Exchange (ESRE)

Over 2024, the DOORS Early-Stage Researcher Exchange (ESRE) programme supported 6 early-career researchers to travel to and from centres of excellence in the Black Sea region and Europe, to collaborate with a mentor and local specialists. They advanced our knowledge in areas such as social sciences, fisheries, biology, ocean modelling and Earth Observation applications.

Image: Photos and Overview of geographical aspects of the ESRE applicants © DOORS

The exchange aimed to build and deepen collaborations and networks. During the exchange, participants travelled to their chosen host institution/company to conduct a collaborative research activity for one working week, working with, and under the guidance of, a nominated mentor, and potentially with members of their team.

At the end of their stage, each participant delivered a focused research collaboration on one, or more, of the following marine and/or coastal-focused research areas: environmental sciences, Earth sciences, biological

sciences, physical sciences, chemical sciences, Information Technology, data sciences, social sciences, economics and/or Blue Economy.

Life-Long Training (LLT) courses: Maximising community access to research

Eurostat defines Life-Long training as “all learning activities undertaken throughout life with the aim of improving knowledge, skills and competences”. Lifelong learning integrates learning and living, covering learning activities for people of all ages (children, young people, adults and the elderly) in all life-wide contexts (family, school, the community, the workplace) and through a variety of modalities (formal, non-formal and informal), corresponding to a broad range of learning needs and demands.

Our LLT courses are making a connection of science and discoveries of DOORS researchers to the wider Black Sea community. Courses developed include insights into harmonising marine data collection in the Black Sea, best practices & standards for marine data curation, how to use the System of Systems for research and for business development, operational Oceanography, Black Sea Natural Gas Hydrates, modelling Black Sea processes, Circular business models and evaluation of sustainable performance, Financials for startups, Business model fundamentals, Startups, Business planning essentials, Strategies for effective communication, Enhancing Capacity with Mutual Mobilisation Learning workshops, Best Practice for Multi-Actor Forums, Ocean Literacy, Citizen Science – all meant to guide the Black Sea researchers, innovators and the commercial start-ups of tomorrow.

The training is available on the DOORS website: www.doorsblacksea.eu. Also, LifeWatch ERIC provided technical support to the delivery and dissemination of the LLT courses. A dedicated section on the LifeWatch ERIC training platform was created under [International Projects - DOORS](#) to host the recordings, presentations and other materials produced by the BSA programme. This solution ensures long term sustainability of the content even after the project ends.

Train the Trainer (TtT)

Training of the trainers builds on the Lifelong Learnings content.

Our Train-the-Trainer (TtT) Workshop brought together educators from across the Black Sea region and other European countries to explore the rich legacy of the DOORS Knowledge Transfer and Training Programme. From blended learning to training management tools, and engaging discussions on the future of Black Sea education, the workshop laid the groundwork for sustainable, impactful learning.

The training is available on the DOORS website: www.doorsblacksea.eu. Also, LifeWatch ERIC provided technical support to the delivery and dissemination of the TtT courses. A dedicated section on the LifeWatch ERIC training platform was created under [International Projects - DOORS](#) to host the recordings, presentations and other materials produced by the BSA programme. This solution ensures long term sustainability of the content even after the project ends.

Connecting Communities: Youth Engagement and Ocean Literacy

Ocean Literacy is an enabler of sustainable development, responsible research and innovation, and engaged citizens. It provides the baseline of the scientific knowledge to a broad range of stakeholders, spanning children and youth, early career scientists, policy and decisionmakers, blue economy businesses, and experts in disciplines not directly connected with marine research, while being of relevance. The DOORS commitment

to raising Black Sea literacy and contribute to the European and global efforts is a substantial asset to develop stronger Ocean Literacy offer worldwide, consolidate and promote best practices, and sustain the project’s legacy. This work also represents an invaluable opportunity to develop new or consolidate existing partnerships across a broad range of areas which are benefiting from DOORS (marine scientific research, blue economy acceleration, training, education, awareness raising, etc).

A **DOORS Ocean Literacy Network** was successfully established at the beginning of 2024 and connections made with the EU4Ocean, UN Ocean Decade, EMSEA, and EU projects BRIDGE-BS, Nautilus, SHORE. It helped DOORS engage with citizens along the pillars of the Black Sea Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (Knowledge Bridge, Blue Economy, Key Infrastructure and Policy Enablers, Empowered Citizens and Enhanced Blue Force), contributing to an increased public awareness about the importance of ocean science and sustainability and promoting the work of DOORS to the broad public.

Overall, the network delivered educational and engagement activities, materials, and events for the Black Sea, while also contributing to a stronger Ocean Literacy offer internationally.

The following audiences were targeted:

- Scientists and science institutions;
- National authorities responsible for marine monitoring and observations, blue economy, and research and development;
- Schools and teachers;
- Aquaria and museums;
- NGOs and foundations;
- Major international and pan-European initiatives on Ocean Literacy;
- European Union institutions.

The network has been convened from a pool of the DOORS consortium partners with expertise and interest in societal engagement and education. It was formed through an open call for expression of interest to the DOORS consortium. Members were selected keeping in mind the spread and representativeness in expertise, geographical representation, and the gender balance, as much as possible.

DOORS has delivered:

- Various ‘Science Meets Education’ and ‘[Open Doors](#)’ events
- Various events linked to the international eco-calendar (i.e., [Earth Hour](#), World Environment Day, European Researchers Night, Green Week)

Images: DOORS at the European Researchers Night, Bucharest & Magurele, Romania 2024 © DOORS

- Stakeholder co-design workshop at the DOORS Stakeholder Conference 2024. Key outcomes included the need for enhanced communication from scientists, greater public and policymaker engagement, and the use of creative approaches in education. The workshop also emphasised the importance of translating materials into local languages, training teachers, and involving youth in communicating scientific information. Barriers such as time constraints and language differences were noted, and the need for financial support to sustain local activities was stressed. The workshop concluded with a call for replicating successful initiatives across other regions and fostering long-term collaborations.

Image: Stakeholder co-design workshop on Ocean Literacy, 24 April 2024, Bucharest © DOORS

- On 1st August 2023, we kickstarted a new Citizen Science programme for [Monitoring Aquatic Species in the Black Sea](#), aiming to introduce Citizen Science Monitoring programme to High School, and early-stage University students.

#BlackSeaMAS Citizen Science for Monitoring Aquatic Species (MAS)

Mission #1 - 3 Native Species English Version

Native species are organisms found in a particular ecosystem or region due to natural processes such as natural distribution. These species play a vital role in maintaining the overall balance and functioning of ecosystems. Therefore, their monitoring allows us to assess and conserve the health of ecosystems, and expand our scientific understanding of the natural world.

Aurelia aurita (moon jellyfish)

Native to the Black Sea, the jellyfish is almost entirely transparent, and can be recognized by its four umbrella-shaped and its four long, thin tentacles. These tentacles, which are used for capturing prey, are visible through the top of the bell. It feeds on planktonic organisms, crustaceans, fish eggs. From coastal to deep waters, it is reported to be able to tolerate wide temperature ranges from 0-25 °C, with optimum of 15-20°C.

Why is monitoring important?
Aerial drifting causes dispersion of eggs, which leads to mass mortalities, algal blooming, and ecosystem overloading.

Where can it be found?
It can be observed in shallow waters, and is covered on the beach, especially in summer.

Rhizostoma pulmo (barrel jellyfish)

Native to the Black Sea, being able to reach 100cm, making it the largest jellyfish in the Black Sea. The color varies, but usually have a pale umbrella-shaped bell with horizontal or vertical stripes. It feeds on planktonic organisms, fish eggs, and small crustaceans. It mostly inhabits coastal waters, where can be found plenty of food. From July to October, at temperatures ranging from 17-20°C.

Why is monitoring important?
Rhizostoma blooming causes oxygen depletion of water, leading to mass fish mortalities, algal blooming, and ecosystem overloading.

Where can it be found?
It can be observed in shallow waters, and is covered on the beach at the end of summer.

Pachygrapsus marmoratus (marmorated rock crab)

Native to the Black Sea, they can have a shell (carapace) length of up to 3.5 cm, which is dark reddish brown with mottling on yellow to white. It is commonly found on rocky shore habitats, emerging from the water during dusk to dawn.

Why is monitoring important?
Large size crabs help to maintain the cleanliness and health of habitats and can indicate a healthy and balanced ecosystem.

Where can it be found?
It is commonly found on rocky shore habitats, emerging from the water during dusk to dawn.

#BlackSeaMAS Citizen Science for Monitoring Aquatic Species (MAS)

Mission #2 - 3 Invasive Species English Version

Invasive species are organisms that are introduced into an ecosystem or region where they are not native. These species can have negative impacts on the environment, economy, and human health. Their monitoring will allow us to better understand their impacts, and implement effective management strategies to minimize their negative effects.

Mya arenaria (soft-shell clam)

The species has a white oval shell which is rounded at the head end. Young clams have a grey, yellow or brown tissue covering the shell. It feeds on microscopic organisms and organic detritus that filters out of the water. It lives buried up to 20 cm below the surface. It appears once or twice a year in the spring or summer, at temperatures of 15-20°C.

Why is monitoring important?
Invasive to the Black Sea, introduced in the 1960s (from North Atlantic) with the soft-shell clam. It is now the only shallow water (15-20 cm) of the native bivalve *Littoridinus littoridinus*.

Where can it be found?
Usually in shallow waters, at bottom of 15-20 cm, and sometimes being introduced on the beach. It can be found on the beach immediately after storms.

Anadara kagoshimensis (soft-shell clam)

The clam has a white or cream colored, thick, oval shell with numerous ribs. The inner surface is highly porous. The right one is smaller than the left one. It lives in the upper part of the water with its gills but also feeds on detritus and organisms in the sediment. The clam lives in waters ranging in temperature between 15°C and 25 °C, tolerating low dissolved oxygen levels.

Why is monitoring important?
Introduced to the Black Sea, accidentally introduced in the '90s probably via ballast water originating from the Indo-Pacific region. It replaced the habitat of several native mollusk species.

Where can it be found?
Usually in shallow coastal areas (0-25 cm), and sometimes being introduced on the beach. It can be found on the beach immediately after storms.

Rapana venosa (Asian rapa whelk)

The species possesses a thick, rounded shell typically about 3cm long. The outer shell is variable in colour, from grey to reddish brown. This shell is a white generalist, capable practically every generalist, replacing practically every native species. The species was first reported in July to September with a temperature window of 15 to 20°C.

Why is monitoring important?
Introduced to the Black Sea, accidentally introduced in the '90s - '00s originating from the East of Europe/China. It has caused the decline of native mollusk populations such as oysters and mussels.

Where can it be found?
Usually in shallow rocky habitats but can also inhabit muddy and sandy areas, being introduced on the beach on the beach immediately after storms.

Image: #BlackSeaMAS worksheets and bookmark © DOORS

The campaign is called [#BlackSeaMAS](#) – Observing and Monitoring Aquatic Species. We developed some teaching materials in the form of two worksheets to aid the study and reporting of invasive and non-invasive species in the region. Despite the lack of available citizen science apps targeting

Black Sea species, we were able to connect with Lewis Stagnetto of The Nautilus project and creator of the 'NEMO' app who kindly agreed to add our target species to his database. This allowed us to demonstrate a simple and user-friendly citizen science reporting tool that allows users to report sightings using their mobile phone with GPS location map and time stamp information.

- [Black Sea in Winter Photo Contest](#), organised for people's frozen moments in time from the Black Sea. The winter season brings many beautiful coastal scenes but also often highlights the impact of climate change through extreme weather events such as storms and increased litter pollution. Featuring submissions from primary school children, adults, professional photographers and scientific researchers, we were able to raise awareness about these changes through the art of photography.

Image: Black Sea in Winter Photo Context Poster © DOORS

Further on, we produced a [40-page book](#) featuring images submitted and descriptions of their connection to the places that matter to them, linking relevant scientific and climate information to specific images. Overall, the Black Sea in Winter Photobook shows how photography can highlight challenges and solutions in relation to sustainable development goals in the Black Sea, improving ocean literacy and our understanding of the role of the ocean in a changing climate.

Image: Black Sea in Winter Photobook © DOORS

Postcards were made from some entries (see below) and distributed at the 1st DOORS Stakeholder Conference 2024, at EMD 2024 and following DOORS events. As additional value, we were able to use one image sent in by Daria-Iulia Milu, a teenager in Constanta, for our 'Love the Ocean' Workshop poster (image bottom left):

Image: Black Sea in Winter Postcards © DOORS

- Explore Marine Life through Upcycled Art

Image: DOORS Explore Marine Life through Upcycled Art event leaflet © DOORS

- [#BlackSeaLitterFree](#) Campaign – Observing and [Monitoring Marine Litter](#) in the Black Sea

Image: DOORS #BlackSeaLitterFree call poster © DOORS

- Observing and Monitoring Microplastics on the Black Sea beaches. Using the specially designed Microplastics Activity Kit and the ANDROMEDA App, volunteers help scientists monitor and collect vital data on microplastics pollution along Black Sea beaches. Participants collect sand samples, isolate microplastic particles using simple tools, and submit their findings via the app, contributing to a European database. This activity raises awareness, supports marine science, and empowers communities to play an active role in protecting the Black Sea environment.

Image: Hands-on activity on the beach, observing plastics and microplastics © DOORS

- [#BlackSeaDolphinWatch](#) Campaign – Observing and Monitoring Black Sea Dolphins

Image: DOORS #BlackSeaDolphinWatch call poster © DOORS

Three species of cetaceans live in the Black Sea, all protected by national and international legislation, each facing unique challenges and requiring collaborative conservation efforts.

The Harbor Porpoise (*Phocoena phocoena relicta*) is the smallest cetacean species in the Black Sea, measuring 1.30–1.60 meters in length. Unlike other dolphins, it has a rounded head and lacks a rostrum. It is very easily startled and avoids interaction with humans, displaying less active surface behavior. It lives in coastal waters, preferring shallow areas.

The Common Dolphin (*Delphinus delphis ponticus*) has a slender body and a length of up to 1.50–2.00 meters. It is recognized for its distinctive coloration, featuring a hourglass pattern on its sides. This dolphin is highly sociable, forming large groups and being known for its acrobatic behaviors. It prefers deep waters but can also be found near the coast.

The Bottlenose Dolphin (*Tursiops truncatus ponticus*) is the largest dolphin species in the Black Sea, with a length of up to 2–2.80 meters. It is robust, with a thick snout, intelligent, and adaptable, often interacting with humans. It is frequently seen in small groups. While it prefers coastal areas, it can also be found in open waters.

A Call for Conservation

All three species play a crucial role in the Black Sea ecosystem, serving as important indicators of marine environmental health. Unfortunately, their populations are threatened by pollution, overfishing, and habitat degradation. Conserving them is essential for maintaining marine biodiversity.

Image: DOORS #BlackSeaDolphinWatch in action © DOORS

In Romania, the volunteer network "Volunteers for Saving Dolphins" - driven largely by passionate school teachers and students - is making a difference! Every month, they patrol the coast, track stranded dolphins, and report their findings with detailed forms. Their dedication is essential for understanding and protecting these amazing creatures.

- DOORS Black Sea [Youth Mobile Film competition](#). Open to young filmmakers aged 14–21, the competition encourages creative storytelling that highlights concerns, hopes, or scientific curiosity about the Black Sea.

Image: DOORS Black Sea Mobile Film competition leaflet © DOORS

- ‘Love the Ocean Future Workshop’ Youth engagement series of Workshops across the Black Sea (24 February 2024 – pilot in Constanta, Romania; and January-March 2025 – across all Black Sea countries in DOORS).

This involved designing an interactive questionnaire in Mentimeter, securing a venue and catering for a 2-hour engagement activity. The workshops aimed to capture the views of high school students on their relationship to the environment, from understanding the science, designing learning activities they want to see happen and exploring potential career paths.

The workshops were both enlightening and rewarding as we explored their aspirations within the framework of the DOORS Ocean Literacy Network and the EuroGOOS #OceanDecade project #Scientists4OceanLiteracy.

Image: DOORS Love the Ocean Future (Pilot) Workshop, 14 February 2024, Constanta - poster (Left) and images (Right) © DOORS

Image: DOORS Love the Ocean Future Workshop, Georgia 2025 © DOORS

Image: DOORS Love the Ocean Future Workshop, Bulgaria 2025 (Left – Burgas; Right – Varna) © DOORS

Image: DOORS Love the Ocean Future Workshop, Türkiye 2025 © DOORS

Image: DOORS Love the Ocean Future Workshop, Romania 2025 © DOORS

Image: DOORS Love the Ocean Future Workshop, Moldova 2025 © DOORS

Image: DOORS Love the Ocean Future Workshop, Ukraine 2025 © DOORS

Why Knowledge Transfer and Training?

How can education connect communities?

Education as an approach to connecting communities is well-documented. Collaborative learning philosophies and collaborative problem solving essentially brings people together, to work on common goals, exchange opinions, clarify confusions and jointly address problems (Hron and Fredrich, 2003).

Importance of group learning

Group learning brings stakeholders together to arrive at comprehensive plans or knowledge outcomes. Various stakeholder groups such as academia, government, public and private industry and average citizens often have conflicting goals, information, views and motivators.

Group Learning brings people together, helping them to focus their attention on the task at hand. Even if someone is not an expert in a certain topic, group learning enables them to work with others who can help

them achieve outcomes they want, de-mystifies issues they formerly perceived as complex, and establishes learning relationships they take forward with them.

With perspectives from different sectors, people who take part in education group learning work can bring their ideas together and reach compromise solutions that can work for all. It is a social approach that works for all generations, and career stages, while founding communities or practice across the region.

Communication as a driver of Impact and Long-Term Learning for all

Effective communication plays a vital role in amplifying the impact and effective, long-term learning.

By educating diverse audiences about the Black Sea's unique challenges and opportunities, informing stakeholders of project milestones, scientific insights, and policy relevance, engaging communities through participatory activities and dialogue, and inspiring action toward sustainability and regional cooperation, DOORS ensures that its outcomes resonate beyond scientific circles.

Strategic, inclusive communication turns data into dialogue, research into policy, and knowledge into action - helping to embed the project's results in future innovation, governance, and public awareness across the Black Sea region and beyond.

Working together for the future

DOORS had generated already several outcomes that will leave a trace in the history of Black Sea Research, Education and for the creation of a Blue Growth Community:

- Harmonisation of existing data, metadata, methodologies at the basin scale are now available for all categories of stakeholders all around the Black Sea, the first step towards a Responsible Open Science, giving FAIR information about the state of the Black Sea.
- Identification of current knowledge gaps and needs regarding data and methods after the dialogue with the relevant policy makers at all levels to facilitate the implementation of environmental policies and strategies; could be used directly from all relevant monitoring agencies in the region.
- The implementation and adoption of the Optical Water Type (OWT) methodology for the Black Sea, is a legacy from DOORS into the Black Sea as it will facilitate a lot the connection of the satellite methodology to match the satellite data products against the most comprehensive in situ validation data set collated for the Black Sea.
- The first ever successful launch of a glider in the Black Sea
- The first ever EC funded survey for the submarine cultural heritage sites in front of the Georgian waters have also been among the first to be performed here.
- The dedicated studies on greenhouse gas emissions on the Bulgarian coastal part, with conclusions on their diurnal and seasonal variability
- The new key observations and how they relate to the current status of the Black Sea Autonomous Observing System, which could eventually help in the future monitoring and scientific issues.
- Reports on the assessment of the impact of methane released from the anoxic sediment and climate change on the Black Sea stratification of the water column and the deep-sea microbial biodiversity which by its own is a unique information that could always be used in the future from different stakeholder groups.
- The unique researchers' exchange which gives the opportunity to 6 individuals the possibility to physical placement in a host institution, under the guidance of a mentor.
- The screening of the educational programmes dedicated to the various aspects of Blue Growth in all Black Sea countries and to the current preparation of a Master that will be specialized in the Blue Growth for the Black Sea.
- The analysis of the ecosystem services for the Black Sea, in a river mouth / coast to the open sea approach and has been the basis for future sustainable blue economy planning.
- Engagement with the renewables companies has been a subsequent logical step with activities still in progress.
- The Multi Actor Fora (MAFs), bringing all categories of stakeholders together in a dialogue where the scientists have proven their role as honest brokers to society and solving of conflicts between users.
- The engagement of different groups of stakeholders, which will leave surely a legacy behind. The 1st DOORS Stakeholder Conference, "Black Sea Futures: Science, Prosperity, and People," took place in Bucharest, featured interactive high-level panels, co-design workshops, and a showcase of Black Sea research and innovation. It provided a platform for exchanging views on the sustainable blue

economy sectors, the development of the Digital Twin Ocean, training, capacity enhancement, youth engagement, and the science-policy interface.

DOORS outcomes in support of the Common Maritime Agenda. The Black Sea Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda turned into action

- Policymakers should consider the important contribution that data harmonisation guidance and intercalibration work, produced by DOORS, can make to ecosystem management and compliance with the EU Marine Strategy Framework (MSFD) in the region's EU member states.
- The capabilities provided through the DOORS System of Systems (SoS) should be promoted as a platform for supporting environmental stewardship and blue economic development.
- The System of System's capability might be taken further by developing a digital twin of the Black Sea, an adaptive, interactive model that mimics the structure, context and behaviour of the Black Sea through real-time data integration. This powerful platform can be used as an engine to trial and support a suite of blue economy opportunities, from land management and conservation to marine navigation and the tourist economy.
- Policymakers, regulators and management authorities should consider adopting – where relevant – the open-source modelling capabilities to support compliance with the Water Framework Directive (WFD) and Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), alongside more comprehensive management of the Black Sea at Sea-scale, including:
 - Wave, morphodynamic and flooding modelling to manage extreme event emergencies, e.g. through early warning systems.
 - Marine litter modelling capabilities to support effective, targeted interventions to prevent, manage, and reduce marine litter.
- Economic policymakers should consider the successes demonstrated through the Black Sea Accelerator (led by the DOORS and BRIDGE-BS Black Sea projects) as a model to help build capacity for blue economy start-ups through targeted support.
- The ongoing importance of shared learning and marine literacy initiatives to foster a communal sense of responsibility and stewardship for the Black Sea's environmental and economic wellbeing should be noted and considered for future initiatives in the region.

Full details of the project's partners and outputs are available on the project website: www.doorsblacksea.eu

To dive deeper into the work, impact, and legacy of the DOORS project, we invite you to explore our range of digital resources designed to educate, inform, and inspire:

- DOORS Research Articles: Access peer-reviewed publications and project outputs on our dedicated Zenodo community page: <https://zenodo.org/communities/doorsblacksea/records>
- Video Library: Watch project highlights, interviews, and educational content on our YouTube channel: www.youtube.com/@doorsblacksea

Stay connected and engaged through our social media platforms:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/doorsblacksea>
- Facebook: <https://facebook.com/doorsblacksea>
- Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/doorsblacksea>

These platforms offer ongoing insights into the DOORS journey, helping stakeholders, researchers, students, and the wider public stay informed and inspired by the transformation of the Black Sea region.

Exploring challenges together is the touch paper for innovation, fresh thinking, and novel solutions. Could your expertise, experience or networks play a formative part in the region's future? We are open to collaboration with different organisations, interests and perspectives to appreciate the full spectrum of opportunities for the region and its people.

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